

Author note on update of article: The economic commitment of climate change

Our paper “The economic commitment of climate change” provided new assessments of the economic impacts of climate change based on three methodological innovations: the use of subnational economic data, the consideration of the variability and extremes of temperature and precipitation in addition to annual averages, and an assessment of the persistence of impacts on economic growth rates. Following publication in *Nature* in April 2024¹ with open-access data and code², there was widespread engagement from the scientific community.

While we would like to emphasize that the original analysis was applied correctly, two critiques were subsequently brought to light. First, the results were found to be disproportionately sensitive to the removal of one country, Uzbekistan, where inaccuracies were noted in the underlying economic data in the period 1995-1999. Furthermore, it was noted that our original analysis underestimated statistical uncertainty due to the spatial auto-correlation present in our data. To address these issues, we have corrected these underlying economic data as part of a wider database update including further quality control checks³. Moreover, we updated our methodology to generally control for data source transitions and higher-order trends as present in the Uzbekistan data (detailed below). This yielded results which are more robust to the removal of individual countries (Fig. 4 below), with a slightly lower median estimate of global damages (17% instead of 19% by mid-century). Accounting for spatial autocorrelations leads to larger uncertainty ranges (likely range of 6-31% instead of 11-29%, methods detailed below) but does not change the median (Fig. 5). Under the new methodological updates, there is a 91% chance of damages being larger than mitigation costs by mid-century.

We here provide an updated version of the manuscript based on these corrections, while noting that this has yet to undergo peer-review. Our central conclusions regarding the divergence of damages across emission scenarios at mid-century (Fig. 1), the relative magnitude of damages and mitigation costs (Fig. 1), the relative contribution of different climate variables (Fig. 2), and the distribution of damages across geographies (Fig. 2) and different economies (Fig. 3) remain unchanged, albeit with higher levels of uncertainty. We further note that these estimates remain qualitatively consistent with earlier and emerging estimates of the economic impacts of climate change and the benefits of emission mitigation⁴⁻¹¹.

For a direct comparison, we show the original and updated main figures next to each other below. In the updated manuscript and supplementary information, we highlight the respective changes to our original paper in blue to facilitate comparison. For that reason, we have also adjusted our analysis and presentation of the divergence of damages across emission scenarios at mid-century: instead of

estimating the time at which damages diverge with a given probability, we estimate the probability of divergence at mid-century. This implies that there is a 90% chance of damages diverging by 2050 compared to a 99% chance as estimated in the original version.

Methodological updates to address critiques

In particular, we have updated our analysis as follows in response to the critiques:

1. Addressing robustness of results

a. Corrected the underlying economic data for Uzbekistan for the years 1995-1999.

Specifically, source data in PPP USD from UNDP Human Development Reports¹²⁻¹⁴ had been inaccurately converted into local currencies using the market exchange instead of purchasing power parity (PPP) rates and then into constant 2015 USD. This resulted in a large discrepancy to data for the period 2000-2019 which came from the National Statistical Agency of Uzbekistan. Our correction of that provided consistent data for the period 2000-2005 for which data from the Statistical Agency and from a UNDP Human Development Report are available. It formed part of a wider update and quality check of the sub-national economic database DOSE which we use, based on further issues reported by users as part of the data set's on-going development. These are documented fully at ref. (3) and result in improved consistency with another researcher-compiled sub-national dataset¹⁵. This is a natural process of database development and one which is also present in national data, for example in the national accounts provided by the World Bank¹⁶.

b. Updated our methodological analysis to include further controls which limit the potential influence of anomalies from data-source transitions and other underlying economic trends.

These updates involve (i) removing data on economic growth which stem from a transition across data sources, and (ii) adding a quadratic term to the regional time trends which are used to control for underlying economic trends (see new text in Methods section for detail). This renders our analysis more robust to the removal of individual countries (see Fig 4 below). The use of quadratic time trends is in line with prominent literature on the economic impacts of climate change^{17,18} and explicitly advocated for by the colleagues who critiqued our analysis, when quadratic trends are present in the underlying economic data¹⁹, which we confirm is the case for the subnational economic data we use (see newly added Supplementary Figure S18 of the updated manuscript).

2. Addressing uncertainty

- a. **Updated our methodological analysis to account for spatial autocorrelation in our data.** We present a range of estimates of specifications to do so using Conley standard errors²⁰ which assume full correlation between regions up to cut-off distances of 500 and 1000km, as well as clustering at the level of country-year (see Fig 5B below and the newly added Supplementary Figure S16 of the updated manuscript). The latter was advocated for by one of the critiques of our study. Based on our analysis of the residuals of our model (see Fig 5A below), we use Conley errors with 500km distance cut-off as our main specification. This is agnostic to the size of countries which varies substantially in our global panel of subnational regions. Rather than bootstrapping, we implement these Conley standard errors in our projections by sampling from the multivariate distribution specified by the covariance matrix of the regression model (see new text in Methods section for detail).

We appreciate the corrective role of the global scientific community and specifically thank Tom Bearpark, Dylan Hogan and Solomon Hsiang as well as Christof Schötz for bringing these issues to our attention. We take full responsibility for the original oversight. By re-feeding our updated manuscript into the research literature with continued open access data and methodology, we hope to contribute to the further development of this important field.

Figures

Figure 1: The commitment and divergence of economic climate damages vs mitigation costs (original left, update right). All figure details are as explained in the original figure caption.

Figure 2. The committed economic damages of climate change by sub-national region and climatic component (original above, updated below). All figure details are as explained in the original figure caption.

Figure 3. The injustice of committed climate damages by cumulative historical emissions and income (original above, updated below). All figure details are as explained in the original figure caption.

Figure 4. Robustness of results to the exclusion of data from Uzbekistan after the methodological updates. Panel a: estimates of the cumulative marginal impact of one degree of warming in annual mean temperature when dropping individual countries from the sample are shown in grey, with the special case of Uzbekistan highlighted in red. Panel b: The distribution of committed global damages for the full data set and having removed data from Uzbekistan either completely or prior to 2000, respectively. The median is indicated by the white bar (17%, 12% and 11%, respectively) which, when removing Uzbekistan, falls within the interquartile range as indicated by the inner box.

Figure 5: Adjustment of standard errors to account for spatial auto-correlation. Panel a: correlations of model residuals between pairs of regions as a function of interregional distance are shown as the individual black dots. The mean value of pairwise correlations within bins of 50km width is shown in red. The preferred cut-off distance of 500km is shown by the vertical dashed blue line. Conley standard errors assume full correlation between regions up to that cut-off distance. Panel b: The distribution of committed global damages is shown for different standard error specifications, using Conley standard errors with cut-offs of 500km and 1000km, and clustering by region or country-year.

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Update to: the economic commitment of climate change

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1 **Global projections of macroeconomic climate-change damages typically consider impacts**
2 **from average annual and national temperatures over long-time horizons¹⁻⁶. Here, we**
3 **utilize recent empirical findings from more than 1600 regions worldwide over the past 40**
4 **years to project sub-national damages from temperature and precipitation including**
5 **daily variability and extremes^{7,8}. Using an empirical approach which provides a robust**
6 **lower-bound on the persistence of impacts on economic growth, we find that the world**
7 **economy is committed to an income reduction of 17% within the next 26 years due to**
8 **historical carbon emissions and socioeconomic inertia (relative to a baseline without**
9 **climate impacts, likely range of 6-31% accounting for physical climate and empirical**
10 **uncertainty). These damages already outweigh the mitigation costs required to limit**
11 **global warming to two degrees by fivefold over this near-term timeframe, and thereafter**
12 **diverge strongly dependent on emission choices. Committed damages arise**
13 **predominantly through changes in average temperature, but accounting for further**
14 **climatic components raises estimates by approximately 26% percent and leads to**
15 **stronger regional heterogeneity. Committed losses are projected for all regions except**
16 **those at very high latitudes, where warming and reductions in temperature variability**
17 **bring benefits. The largest losses are committed at lower latitudes in regions with lower**
18 **cumulative historical emissions and lower present-day income.**

19 Projections of the macroeconomic damage caused by future climate change are crucial to
20 informing public and policy debates regarding adaptation, mitigation and climate justice. On
21 the one hand, adaptation against climate impacts must be justified and planned on the basis of
22 an understanding of their future magnitude and spatial distribution⁹. This is also of importance
23 in the context of climate justice¹⁰, as well as to key societal actors including governments,
24 central banks and private businesses which increasingly require the inclusion of climate risks
25 in their macroeconomic forecasts to aid adaptive decision making^{11,12}. On the other hand,
26 climate mitigation policy such as the Paris Climate Agreement is often evaluated by balancing
27 the costs of its implementation against the benefits of avoiding projected physical damages.
28 This evaluation occurs both formally via cost-benefit analyses^{1,4-6}, as well as informally via
29 public perception of mitigation and damage costs¹³.

30 Projections of future damages meet challenges when informing these debates, in particular the
31 human biases relating to uncertainty and remoteness which are raised by long-term
32 perspectives¹⁴. Here we aim to overcome such challenges, by assessing the extent of economic
33 damages from climate change to which the world is already committed by historical emissions
34 and socioeconomic inertia (the range of future emission scenarios which are considered
35 socioeconomically plausible¹⁵). Such a focus on the near-term limits the large uncertainties
36 regarding diverging future emission trajectories, the resulting long-term climate response, and
37 the validity of applying historically observed climate-economic relations over long timescales
38 during which socio-technical conditions may change considerably. As such, this focus aims to
39 simplify the communication and maximize the credibility of projected economic damages from
40 future climate change.

41 In projecting the future economic damages from climate change, we make use of recent
42 advances in climate econometrics which provide evidence for impacts on sub-national
43 economic growth from numerous components of the distribution of daily temperature and

44 precipitation^{3,7,8}. Using fixed effects panel regression models to control for potential
45 confounders, these studies exploit within-region variation in local temperature and
46 precipitation in a panel of more than 1600 regions worldwide, comprising climate and income
47 data over the past 40 years to identify the plausibly causal effects of changes in several climate
48 variables on economic productivity^{16,17}. Specifically, macroeconomic impacts have been
49 identified from changing daily temperature variability, total annual precipitation, the annual
50 number of wet days and extreme daily rainfall which occur in addition to those already
51 identified from changing average temperature^{2,3,18}. Moreover, regional heterogeneity in these
52 effects based on the prevailing local climatic conditions has been found using interactions
53 terms. The selection of these climate variables follows micro-level evidence for mechanisms
54 related to the impacts of average temperatures on labor and agricultural productivity², of
55 temperature variability on agricultural productivity and health⁷, as well as of precipitation on
56 agricultural, labor outcomes, and flood damages⁸ (see Extended Data Table 1 for an overview
57 including more detailed references). Refs. ^{7,8} contain a more detailed motivation for the use of
58 these particular climate variables and provide extensive empirical tests regarding the
59 robustness and nature of their effects on economic output which are summarized in our
60 methods section. By accounting for these additional climatic variables at the sub-national level,
61 we aim for a more comprehensive description of climate impacts with greater detail across both
62 time and space.

63 **Constraining the persistence of impacts**

64 A key determinant and source of discrepancy in estimates of the magnitude of future climate
65 damages is the extent to which the impact of a climate variable on economic growth rates
66 persists. The two extreme cases in which these impacts persist indefinitely or only
67 instantaneously are commonly referred to as growth or level effects^{19,20} (see methods section
68 “Empirical specification – fixed-effects distributed lag model” for mathematical definitions).

69 Recent work shows that future damages from climate change depend strongly on whether
70 growth or level effects are assumed²⁰. Following refs. (2,18), we provide constraints on this
71 persistence by using distributed lag models to test the significance of delayed effects separately
72 for each climate variable. Importantly and in contrast to refs (2,18), we use climate variables in
73 their first-differenced form following ref. 3, implying a dependence of the growth rate on a
74 change in climate variables. This choice means that a baseline specification without any lags
75 constitutes a model prior of purely level effects, in which a permanent change in the climate
76 has only an instantaneous effect on the growth rate^{3,19,21}. By including lags, one can then test
77 whether any effects may persist further. This is in contrast to the specification used by refs. 2,18
78 in which climate variables are used without taking the first difference, implying a dependence
79 of the growth rate on the level of climate variables. In this alternative case, the baseline
80 specification without any lags constitutes a model prior of pure growth effects, in which a
81 change in climate has an infinitely persistent effect on the growth rate. Consequently, including
82 further lags in this alternative case tests whether the initial growth impact is recovered^{18,19,21}.
83 Both of these specifications suffer from the limiting possibility that if too few lags are included,
84 one might falsely accept the model prior. The limitations of including a very large number of
85 lags, including loss of data and increasing statistical uncertainty with an increasing number of
86 parameters, means that such a possibility is likely. By choosing a specification in which the
87 model prior is one of level effects, our approach is therefore conservative by design, avoiding
88 assumptions of infinite persistence of climate impacts on growth and instead providing a lower-
89 bound on this persistence based on what is observable empirically (see methods section
90 “Empirical specification – fixed-effects distributed lag model” for further exposition of this
91 framework). The conservative nature of such a choice is likely the reason that ref. 19 finds much
92 greater consistency between the impacts projected by models which use the first difference of
93 climate variables as opposed to their levels.

94 We begin our empirical analysis of the persistence of climate impacts on growth using ten lags
95 of the first-differenced climate variables in fixed-effects distributed lag models. We detect
96 substantial effects on economic growth at time lags of up to approximately eight to ten years
97 for the temperature terms, and up to approximately four years for the precipitation terms
98 (Extended Data Figure 1, Extended Data Table 2).

99 Evaluation by means of Information Criteria indicates that the inclusion of all five climate
100 variables and the use of these numbers of lags provide a preferable trade-off between best-
101 fitting the data and including additional terms which could cause overfitting, in comparison to
102 model specifications excluding climate variables or including more or fewer lags (Extended
103 Data Figure 2, Supplementary Methods Section S1, and Supplementary Table 1). We therefore
104 remove unimportant terms at later lags (Supplementary Figures 1-3 and Supplementary Tables
105 2-4). Further tests using Monte-Carlo simulations demonstrate that the empirical models are
106 robust to autocorrelation in the lagged climate variables (Supplementary Methods Section S2,
107 Supplementary Figures 4 & 5), that Information Criteria provide an effective indicator for lag
108 selection (Supplementary Methods Section S2, Supplementary Figure 6), that the results are
109 robust to concerns of imperfect multi-collinearity between climate variables and that including
110 several climate variables is actually necessary to isolate their separate effects (Supplementary
111 Methods Section S3, Supplementary Figure 7). We provide a further robustness check using a
112 restricted distributed lag model to limit oscillations in the lagged parameter estimates which
113 may result from autocorrelation, finding that it provides similar estimates of cumulative
114 marginal effects to the un-restricted model (Supplementary Methods Section S4,
115 Supplementary Figures 8 & 9). Finally, to explicitly account for any outstanding uncertainty
116 arising from the precise choice of the number of lags, we include empirical models with
117 marginally different numbers of lags in the error sampling procedure of our projection of future
118 damages. On the basis of the lag selection procedure (the [distribution](#) of lagged terms in

119 Extended Data Figure 1 and Extended Data Table 2, as well as Information Criteria in Extended
120 Data Figure 2), we sample from models with eight to ten lags for temperature and four for
121 precipitation (models shown in Supplementary Figures 1-3 and Supplementary Tables 2-4). In
122 summary, this empirical approach to constrain the persistence of climate impacts on economic
123 growth rates is conservative by design in avoiding assumptions of infinite persistence, but
124 nevertheless provides a lower bound on the extent of impact persistence which is robust to the
125 numerous tests outlined above.

126 **Committed damages until mid-century**

127 We combine these empirical economic response functions (Supplementary Figures 1-3 and
128 Supplementary Tables 2-4) with an ensemble of twenty-one climate models (see
129 Supplementary Table 5) from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase-6 (CMIP-6)²²
130 to project the macroeconomic damages from these multiple components of physical climate
131 change (see methods for further details). Bias-adjusted climate models which provide a highly
132 accurate reproduction of observed climatological patterns with limited uncertainty
133 (Supplementary Table 6) are used to avoid introducing biases in the projections. Following a
134 well-developed literature^{2,3,19}, these projections do not aim to provide a prediction of future
135 economic growth. Instead, they are a projection of the exogenous impact of future climate
136 conditions on the economy relative to the baselines specified by socioeconomic projections,
137 based on the plausibly causal relationships inferred by the empirical models, and assuming
138 ceteris paribus. Other exogenous factors relevant for the prediction of economic output are
139 purposefully assumed constant.

140 A Monte-Carlo procedure which samples from climate model projections, empirical models
141 with different numbers of lags, and model parameter estimates (obtained by [sampling from the](#)
142 [covariance matrix](#) of each of the regressions in Supplementary Figures 1-3 and Supplementary
143 Tables 2-4, [which account for spatial autocorrelation up to 500km](#)) is used to estimate the

144 combined uncertainty from these multiple sources. Given these uncertainty distributions, we
145 find that projected global damages **diverge with a statistical likelihood of 10% by mid-century**
146 **(2050, Figure 1)**. As such, the climate damages occurring before this time constitute those to
147 which the world is already committed due to the combination of past emissions and the range
148 of future emission scenarios which are considered socioeconomically plausible¹⁵. These
149 committed damages comprise a permanent income reduction of 17% on average globally
150 (population weighted average) in comparison to a baseline without climate change impacts
151 (with a likely range of **6-31%**, following the likelihood classification adopted by the
152 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), see caption of Figure 1). Even though
153 levels of income per capita generally still increase relative to those today, this constitutes a
154 permanent income reduction for the majority of regions, including North America and Europe
155 (with median income reductions of approximately **8 and 7% respectively**) and with South Asia
156 and Africa being the most strongly affected (with median income reductions of approximately
157 **22 and 21 respectively**; Figure 1). Under a middle-of-the road scenario of future income
158 development (SSP2), this corresponds to global annual damages in **2050 of 32** trillion in 2005
159 International Dollars (likely range of **8-60** trillion 2005 International Dollars). Compared to
160 empirical specifications which assume pure growth or pure level effects, our preferred
161 specification which provides a robust lower-bound on the extent of climate impact persistence
162 produces damages between these two extreme assumptions (Extended Data Figure 3).

163 **Damages already outweigh mitigation costs**

164 We compare the damages to which the world is committed over the next 25 years to estimates
165 of the mitigation costs required to achieve the Paris Climate Agreement. Taking estimates of
166 mitigation costs from the three Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) in the IPCC AR6
167 database²³ which provide results under comparable scenarios (SSP2 baseline, and SSP2-
168 RCP2.6), we find that the median committed climate damages are larger than the median

169 mitigation costs in 2050 (six trillion in 2005 International dollars) by a factor of approximately
170 [five](#). This comparison aims simply to compare the magnitude of future damages against
171 mitigation costs, rather than to conduct a formal cost-benefit analysis of transitioning from one
172 emission path to another. Formal cost-benefit analyses typically find that the net benefits of
173 mitigation only emerge after 2050⁵, which may lead some to conclude that physical damages
174 from climate change are simply not large enough to outweigh mitigation costs until the latter
175 half of the century. Our simple comparison of their magnitudes makes clear that damages are
176 actually already considerably larger than mitigation costs, and the delayed emergence of net
177 mitigation benefits results primarily from the fact that damages across different emission paths
178 are indistinguishable until mid-century (Figure 1).

179 While these near-term damages constitute those to which the world is already committed, we
180 note that damage estimates diverge strongly across emission scenarios after 2050, conveying
181 the clear benefits of mitigation from a purely economic point of view which have been
182 emphasised in previous studies^{4,24}. In addition to the uncertainties assessed in Figure 1, these
183 conclusions are robust to structural choices such as the timescale with which changes in the
184 moderating variables of the empirical models are estimated (Supplementary Figures 10 & 11)
185 [the choice of error scheme used for the empirical models \(Supplementary Figure 16\), and to](#)
186 [removing data from individual countries including Uzbekistan where inaccuracies in the](#)
187 [underlying data sources have been noted and since corrected \(Supplementary Figures 15\).](#)

188 **Damages from variability and extremes**

189 Committed damages primarily arise through changes in average temperature (Figure 2). This
190 reflects the fact that projected changes in average temperature are larger than those in other
191 climate variables when expressed as a function of their historical interannual variability
192 (Extended Data Figure 4). Since the historical variability is that on which the empirical models
193 are estimated, larger projected changes in comparison to this variability are likely to lead to

194 larger future impacts in a purely statistical sense. From a mechanistic perspective, one may
195 plausibly interpret this result as implying that future changes in average temperature are the
196 most unprecedented from the perspective of the historical fluctuations to which the economy
197 is accustomed, and therefore will cause the most damage. This insight may prove useful in
198 terms of guiding adaptation measures to the sources of greatest damage.

199 Nevertheless, future damages based on empirical models which consider changes in annual
200 average temperature only and exclude the other climate variables constitute income reductions
201 of only 14% in 2050 (Extended Data Figure 5a, likely range 4-26%). This suggests that
202 accounting for the other components of the distribution of temperature and precipitation raises
203 net damages by 26%. This increase arises through the additional damages which these climatic
204 components cause, but also because their inclusion reveals a stronger negative economic
205 response to average temperatures (Extended Data Figure 5b). The latter finding is consistent
206 with our Monte-Carlo simulations which suggest that the magnitude of the effect of average
207 temperature on economic growth is underestimated unless accounting for the impacts of other
208 correlated climate variables (Supplementary Figure 7).

209 In terms of the relative contributions of the different climatic components to overall damages,
210 we find that accounting for daily temperature variability causes the largest increase in overall
211 damages relative to empirical frameworks which only consider changes in annual average
212 temperature (2.7 percentage points, equivalent to approximately 5 trillion International
213 Dollars). Accounting for precipitation causes smaller increases in overall damages which are
214 nevertheless equivalent to approximately 2 trillion International Dollars: -0.27 percentage
215 points, -0.76 percentage points and +1.3 percentage points changes in % damages from total
216 annual precipitation, the number of wet days and extreme daily precipitation, respectively.
217 Moreover, climate models appear to underestimate future changes in temperature variability²⁵

218 and extreme precipitation^{26,27} in response to anthropogenic forcing as compared to that
219 observed historically, suggesting that the true impacts from these variables may be larger.

220 **The distribution of committed damages**

221 The spatial distribution of committed damages (Figure 2a) reflects a complex interplay between
222 the patterns of future change in multiple climatic components and those of historical economic
223 vulnerability to changes in those variables. Damages due to increasing annual mean
224 temperature (Figure 2b) are negative almost everywhere globally, and larger at lower latitudes
225 in regions where temperatures are already higher and economic vulnerability to temperature
226 increases is greatest (see the response heterogeneity to mean temperature embodied in
227 Extended Data Figure 1a). This occurs despite the amplified warming projected at higher
228 latitudes²⁸, suggesting that regional heterogeneity in economic vulnerability to temperature
229 changes outweighs heterogeneity in the magnitude of future warming (Supplementary Figure
230 13a). Economic damages due to daily temperature variability (Figure 2c) exhibit a strong
231 latitudinal polarisation, primarily reflecting the physical response of daily variability to
232 greenhouse forcing in which increases in variability across lower latitudes (and Europe)
233 contrast decreases at high latitudes (Supplementary Figure 13b)²⁵. These two temperature
234 terms are the dominant determinants of the pattern of overall damages (Figure 2a), which
235 exhibits a strong polarity with damages across most of the globe except at the high northern
236 latitudes. Future changes in total annual precipitation mainly bring economic benefits except
237 in regions of drying such as the Mediterranean and central South America (Figure 2d,
238 Supplementary Figure 13c), but these benefits are opposed by changes in the number of wet
239 days, which produce damages with a similar pattern of opposite sign (Figure 2e, Supplementary
240 Figure 13d). By contrast, changes in extreme daily rainfall produce damages in all regions,
241 reflecting the intensification of daily rainfall extremes over global land areas^{29,30} (Figure 2f,
242 Supplementary Figure 13e).

243 The spatial distribution of committed damages implies considerable injustice along two
244 dimensions: culpability for the historical emissions which have caused climate change, and
245 pre-existing levels of socio-economic welfare. Spearman's rank correlations indicate that
246 committed damages are significantly larger in countries with smaller historical cumulative
247 emissions, as well as in regions with lower current income per capita (Figure 3). This implies
248 that those countries which will suffer the most from the damages which are already committed
249 are those which are least responsible for climate change, and which also have the least
250 resources to adapt to it.

251 To further quantify this heterogeneity, we assess the difference in committed damages between
252 the upper and lower quartiles of regions when ranked by present income levels and historical
253 cumulative emissions (using a population weighting to both define the quartiles and estimate
254 the group averages). On average, the quartile of countries with lower income are committed to
255 an income loss which is 13.6 percentage points (or 140%) greater than the upper quartile
256 (Extended Data Figure 6), with a likely range of 6-22 percentage points across the uncertainty
257 sampling of our damage projections (following the likelihood classification adopted by the
258 IPCC). Similarly, the quartile of countries with lower historical cumulative emissions are
259 committed to an income loss which is 5.7 percentage-points (or 35) greater than the upper
260 quartile, with a likely range of -1-14 percentage-points. These patterns re-emphasise the
261 prevalence of injustice in climate impacts³¹⁻³³ in the context of the damages to which the world
262 is already committed by historical emissions and socio-economic inertia.

263 **Contextualising the magnitude of damages**

264 The magnitude of projected economic damages exceeds previous literature estimates^{2,3}, arising
265 from a number of developments made upon previous approaches. Our estimates are larger than
266 those of ref.² (see first row of Extended Data Table 3) primarily due to the facts that sub-
267 national estimates typically show a steeper temperature response (see also refs. ^{3,34}) and that

268 accounting for other climatic components raises damage estimates (Extended Data Figure 5).
269 However, we note that our empirical approach using first-differenced climate variables is
270 conservative compared to that of ref. ² with regards to the persistence of climate impacts on
271 growth (see introduction and methods section “Empirical specification – fixed-effects
272 distributed lag model”), an important determinant of the magnitude of long-term damages^{19,21}.
273 Using a similar empirical specification to ref. ² which assumes infinite persistence while
274 maintaining the rest of our approach (sub-national data and additional climate variables),
275 produces considerably larger damages (purple curve of Extended Data Figure 3). Compared to
276 studies which do take the first-difference of climate variables^{3,35}, our estimates are also larger
277 (see second and third rows of Extended Data Table 3). The inclusion of additional climate
278 variables (Extended Data Figure 5) and a sufficient number of lags to more adequately capture
279 the extent of impact persistence (Extended Data Figures 1 & 2) are major sources of this
280 difference, as is the use of specifications which capture non-linearities in the temperature
281 response when compared to ref. ³⁵. In summary, our estimates develop upon previous studies
282 by incorporating the latest data and empirical insights^{7,8}, as well as in providing a robust
283 empirical lower-bound on the persistence of impacts on economic growth, which constitutes a
284 middle ground between the extremes of the growth-vs-levels debate^{19,21} (Extended Data Figure
285 3).

286
287 Compared to the fraction of variance explained by the empirical models historically (<5%), the
288 projection of reductions in income of 17% may appear large. This arises due to the fact that
289 projected changes in climatic conditions are much larger than those which were experienced
290 historically, particularly for changes in average temperature (Extended Data Figure 4). As such,
291 any assessment of future climate change impacts necessarily requires an extrapolation outside
292 of the range of the historical data on which the empirical impact models were evaluated.

293 Nevertheless, these models constitute the most state-of-the-art methods for inference of
294 plausibly causal climate impacts based on observed data. Moreover, we take explicit steps to
295 limit out-of-sample extrapolation by capping the moderating variables of the interaction terms
296 at the 95th percentile of the historical distribution (see methods). This avoids extrapolating the
297 marginal effects outside of what was observed historically. Given the non-linear response of
298 economic output to annual mean temperature (Extended Data Fig.1, Extended Data Table 2),
299 this is a conservative choice which limits the magnitude of damages which we project.
300 Furthermore, back-of-the-envelope calculations indicate that the projected damages are
301 consistent with the magnitude and patterns of historical economic development (see
302 Supplementary Discussion Section S5).

303 **Missing impacts and spatial spill-overs**

304 Despite assessing multiple climatic components from which economic impacts have recently
305 been identified^{3,7,8}, this assessment of aggregate climate damages should not be considered
306 comprehensive. Important channels such as impacts from heatwaves, sea-level rise³⁶, tropical
307 cyclones³⁷ and tipping points^{38,39}, as well as non-market damages such as those to ecosystems⁴⁰
308 and human health⁴¹ are not considered in these estimates. Sea-level rise is unlikely to be
309 feasibly incorporated into empirical assessments such as this since historical sea level
310 variability is mostly unimportant. Non-market damages are inherently intractable within our
311 estimates of impacts on aggregate monetary output and estimates of these impacts could
312 arguably be considered as additional to those identified here. Recent empirical work suggests
313 that accounting for these channels would likely raise estimates of these committed damages
314 with larger damages continuing to arise in the global south^{31,36-42}.

315 Moreover, our main empirical analysis does not explicitly evaluate the potential for impacts in
316 local regions to produce effects which “spill-over” into other regions. Such effects may
317 additionally mitigate or amplify the impacts we estimate, for example if firms relocate

318 production from one affected region to another or if impacts propagate along supply chains.
319 Current literature indicates that trade plays a major role in propagating spill-over effects^{43,44},
320 making their assessment at the sub-national level challenging without available data on sub-
321 national trade dependencies. Studies accounting only for spatially-adjacent neighbours indicate
322 that negative impacts in one region induce further negative impacts in neighbouring regions⁴⁵⁻
323 ⁴⁸, suggesting that our projected damages are likely conservative by excluding these effects. In
324 Supplementary Figure 14 we assess spill-overs from neighbouring regions using a spatial-lag
325 model. For simplicity, this analysis excludes temporal lags, focussing only on
326 contemporaneous effects. The results show that accounting for spatial spill-overs can **in some**
327 **cases** amplify the overall magnitude **of cumulative effects**, and also the heterogeneity, of
328 impacts. Consistent with previous literature, this indicates that the overall magnitude (Figure
329 1) and heterogeneity (Figure 3) of damages which we project in our main specification may be
330 conservative without explicitly accounting for spill-overs. We note that further analysis which
331 addresses both spatial- and trade-connected spill-overs, while also accounting for delayed
332 impacts using temporal lags, would be necessary to adequately address this question fully.
333 These approaches offer fruitful avenues for further research but are beyond the scope of the
334 present manuscript which aims primarily to explore the impacts of different climate conditions
335 and their persistence.

336 **Policy implications**

337 We find that the economic damages due to climate change until 2050 are those to which the
338 world economy is already committed, and that these greatly outweigh the costs required to
339 mitigate emissions in line with the 2C target of the Paris Climate Agreement (Figure 1). This
340 assessment is complementary to formal analyses of the net costs and benefits associated with
341 moving from one emission path to another, which typically find that net benefits of mitigation
342 only emerge in the latter half of the century⁵. Our simple comparison of the magnitude of

343 damages and mitigation costs makes clear that this is primarily because damages are
344 indistinguishable across emissions scenarios – i.e. committed - until mid-century (Figure 1),
345 and that they are actually already much larger than mitigation costs. For simplicity and due to
346 the availability of data, we compare damages to mitigation costs at the global level. Regional
347 estimates of mitigation costs may shed further light on the national incentives for mitigation to
348 which our results already hint, of relevance for international climate policy. While these
349 damages are committed from a mitigation perspective, adaptation may provide an opportunity
350 to reduce them. Moreover, the strong divergence of damages after mid-century reemphasises
351 the clear benefits of mitigation from a purely economic perspective as emphasised in previous
352 studies^{1,4,6,24}.

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492

493 **Figure 1. The commitment and divergence of economic climate damages vs mitigation**
 494 **costs.** Estimates of the projected reduction in income per capita from changes in all climate
 495 variables based on empirical models of climate impacts on economic output with a robust
 496 lower-bound on their persistence (Extended Data Figure 1) under a low-emission scenario
 497 compatible with the 2C warming target and a high-emission scenario (SSP2-RCP2.6 and
 498 SSP5-RCP8.5 respectively) are shown in purple and orange respectively. Shading represents
 499 the 34% and 10% confidence intervals reflecting the *likely* and *very likely* ranges respectively
 500 (following the likelihood classification adopted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate
 501 Change), having estimated uncertainty from a Monte-Carlo procedure which samples the
 502 uncertainty from both the choice of physical climate models, empirical models with different

503 numbers of lags, and bootstrapped estimates of the regression parameters shown in
504 Supplementary Figure 1-3. Vertical dashed line shows the time at which the climate damages
505 of the two emission scenarios diverge with the likelihood indicated in the legend, based on
506 the distribution of differences between emission scenarios arising from the uncertainty
507 sampling discussed above. Note that uncertainty in the *difference* of the two scenarios is
508 smaller than the combined uncertainty of the two respective scenarios because samples of the
509 uncertainty (climate model and empirical model specification and parameter uncertainty) are
510 consistent across the two emission scenarios; hence the divergence of damages occurs while
511 the uncertainty bounds of the two separate damage scenarios still overlap. Estimates of global
512 mitigation costs from the three Integrated Assessment Models which provide results for the
513 SSP2 baseline and SSP2-RCP2.6 scenario are shown in light green in the upper panel, with
514 the median of these estimates shown in bold.

515

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517

518 **Figure 2. The committed economic damages of climate change by sub-national region**

519 **and climatic component.** Estimates of the median projected reduction in sub-national

520 income per capita across emission scenarios (SSP2-RCP2.6 and SSP2-RCP8.5) as well as

521 climate model, empirical model and model parameter uncertainty in the year at which climate

522 damages diverge with 90% likelihood (2050, as identified in Figure 1). Panel (a) shows the

523 impacts arising from all climate variables, while panels (b-f) show the impacts arising

524 separately from changes in annual mean temperature, daily temperature variability, total

525 annual precipitation, the annual number of wet days (>1mm) and extreme daily rainfall

526 respectively (see methods for further definitions). Data on national administrative boundaries

527 are obtained from the GADM database version 3.6 and are freely available for academic use

528 (<https://gadm.org/>).

529

530

531 **Figure 3. The injustice of committed climate damages by cumulative historical**
 532 **emissions and income.** Estimates of the median projected change in national income per
 533 capita across emission scenarios (RCP2.6 and RCP8.5) as well as climate model, empirical
 534 model and model parameter uncertainty in the year at which climate damages diverge *with*
 535 *90% likelihood (2050*, as identified in Figure 1), are plotted against national cumulative
 536 emissions per capita in 2020 (from the Global Carbon Project) and coloured by national
 537 income per capita in 2020 (from the World Bank) in panel (a), and vice versa in panel (b). In
 538 each panel, the size of each scatter point is weighted by the national population in 2020 (from
 539 the World Bank). Inset Figures indicate the Spearman's rank correlation, ρ , and p-values for
 540 a hypothesis test whose null hypothesis is of no correlation, as well as the Spearman's rank
 541 correlation weighted by national population.

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544

545 **Methods**

546 **Historical climate data**

547 Historical daily 2-m temperature and precipitation totals (in mm) are obtained for the period
548 1979-2019 from the W5E5 database. W5E5 stems from ERA-5, a state-of-the-art reanalysis of
549 historical observations, but has been bias-adjusted by applying version 2.0 of the WATCH
550 Forcing Data to ERA-5 reanalysis data, and precipitation data from version 2.3 of the Global
551 Precipitation Climatology Project to better reflect ground-based measurements⁴⁹⁻⁵¹. We obtain
552 this data on a 0.5-by-0.5-degree grid from the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison
553 Project (ISIMIP) database. Importantly, this historical data has been used to bias-adjust future
554 climate projections from CMIP-6 (see the following section), ensuring consistency between
555 the distribution of historical daily weather on which our empirical models were estimated, and
556 the climate projections used to estimate future damages. These data are publicly available from
557 the ISIMIP database. See refs. ^{7,8} for robustness tests of the empirical models to the choice of
558 climate data reanalysis products.

559 **Future climate data**

560 Daily 2-m temperature and precipitation totals (in mm) are taken from 21 climate models
561 participating
562 in CMIP-6 under a high (RCP8.5) and a low (RCP2.6) greenhouse gas emission scenario
563 from 2015-2100. The data have been bias-adjusted and statistically downscaled to a common
564 half-degree grid to reflect the historical distribution of daily temperature and precipitation of
565 the W5E5 dataset using the trend-preserving method developed by ISIMIP^{50,52}. As such, the
566 climate model data reproduces observed climatological patterns exceptionally well
567 (Supplementary Table 5). Gridded data are publicly available from the ISIMIP database.

568 **Historical economic data**

569 Historical economic data stem from the DOSE database of sub-national economic output⁵³. We
570 use [the most](#) recent update to DOSE⁵⁴ ([Dose v2.11](#)) which provides data across 83 countries,
571 1660 sub-national regions with varying temporal coverage from 1960-2019. Sub-national units
572 constitute the first administrative division below national, e.g., states for the USA and
573 provinces for China. Data stem from measures of gross-regional product per capita (GRPpc)
574 or income per-capita in local currencies, reflecting the values reported in national statistical
575 agencies, yearbooks and, in some cases, academic literature. [In cases where a region's time](#)
576 [series is informed by different data sources, we remove data for years in which economic](#)
577 [growth rates would be estimated by comparison of data from two different sources](#). We follow
578 previous literature ^{3,7,8,55} and assess real sub-national output per capita by first converting
579 values from local currencies to US dollars to account for diverging national inflationary
580 tendencies, and then account for US inflation using a US deflator. Alternatively, one might
581 first account for national inflation and then convert between currencies. Supplementary Figure
582 12 demonstrates that our conclusions are [qualitatively](#) consistent when accounting for price
583 changes in the reversed order [and using 10 lags](#), although the magnitude of estimated damages
584 [is substantially smaller and uncertainty increases](#). See the documentation of DOSE for further
585 discussion of these choices. Conversions between currencies are conducted using exchange
586 rates from the FRED database of the Federal Reserve Bank of St Louis⁵⁶ and the national
587 deflators from the World Bank⁵⁷.

588 **Future socioeconomic data**

589 Baseline gridded GDP and population data for the period 2015-2100 are taken from the middle-
590 of-the-road Shared Socioeconomic Pathway scenario SSP2¹⁵. Population data have been
591 downscaled to a half-degree grid by ISIMIP following the methodologies of refs. ^{58,59}, which
592 we then aggregate to the sub-national level of our economic data using the spatial aggregation
593 procedure described below. Since current methodologies for downscaling GDP of the SSPs use

594 downscaled population to do so, per capita estimates of GDP with a realistic distribution at the
595 sub-national level are not readily available for the SSPs. We therefore use national-level GDP
596 per capita projections for all sub-national regions of a given country, assuming homogeneity
597 within countries in terms of baseline GDP per-capita. Here, we use projections which have
598 been updated to account for the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the trajectory of future
599 income, while remaining consistent with the long-term development of the SSPs⁶⁰. The choice
600 of baseline SSP alters the magnitude of projected climate damages in monetary terms, but when
601 assessed in terms of percentage change from the baseline, the choice of socioeconomic scenario
602 is inconsequential. Gridded SSP population data and national level GDP per capita data are
603 publicly available from the ISIMIP database. Sub-national estimates as used in this study are
604 available in the code and data replication files.

605 **Climate variables**

606 Following recent literature^{3,7,8} we calculate an array of climate variables for which substantial
607 impacts on macro-economic output have been identified empirically, supported by further
608 evidence at the micro-level for plausible underlying mechanisms. Please see refs. ^{7,8} for an
609 extensive motivation for the use of these particular climate variables and for detailed empirical
610 tests regarding the nature and robustness of their effects on economic output. To summarize,
611 these studies have found evidence for independent impacts on economic growth rates from
612 annual average temperature, daily temperature variability, total annual precipitation, the annual
613 number of wet days and extreme daily rainfall. Assessments of daily temperature variability
614 were motivated by evidence of impacts on agricultural output and human health, as well as
615 macroeconomic literature on the impacts of volatility on growth when manifest in different
616 dimensions such as government spending, exchange rates and even output itself⁷. Assessments
617 of precipitation impacts were motivated by evidence of impacts on agricultural productivity,
618 metropolitan labor outcomes and conflict, as well as damages caused by flash flooding⁸. See

619 Extended Data Table 1 for detailed references to empirical studies of these physical
620 mechanisms. Marked impacts of daily temperature variability, total annual precipitation, the
621 number of wet days and extreme daily rainfall on macroeconomic output were identified
622 robustly across different climate data-sets, spatial aggregation schemes, specifications of
623 regional time-trends, and error-clustering approaches. They were also found to be robust to the
624 consideration of temperature extremes^{7,8}. Furthermore, these climate variables were identified
625 as having independent effects on economic output^{7,8}, which we further elucidate here using
626 Monte-Carlo simulations to demonstrate the robustness of the results to concerns of imperfect
627 multi-collinearity between climate variables (Supplementary Methods Section S2), as well as
628 by using Information Criteria (Supplementary Table 1) to demonstrate that including several
629 lagged climate variables provides a preferable trade-off between optimally describing the data
630 and limiting the possibility of overfitting.

631 We calculate these variables from the distribution of daily, d , temperature, $T_{x,d}$, and
632 precipitation, $P_{x,d}$, at the grid-cell, x , level for both the historical and future climate data. In
633 addition to annual mean temperature, $\bar{T}_{x,y}$, and annual total precipitation, $P_{x,y}$, we calculate
634 annual, y , measures of daily temperature variability, $\tilde{T}_{x,y}$:

$$635 \quad \tilde{T}_{x,y} = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{m=1}^{12} \sqrt{\frac{1}{D_m} \sum_{d=1}^{D_m} (T_{x,d,m,y} - \bar{T}_{x,m})^2}, \quad (1)$$

636 the number of wet days, $Pwd_{x,y}$:

$$637 \quad Pwd_{x,y} = \sum_{d=1}^{D_y} H(P_{x,d} - 1mm), \quad (2)$$

638 and extreme daily rainfall:

$$639 \quad Pext_{x,y} = \sum_{d=1}^{D_y} H(P_{x,d} - P99.9_x) \cdot P_{x,d}, \quad (3)$$

640 where $T_{x,d,m,y}$ is the grid-cell specific daily temperature in month m and year y , $\bar{T}_{x,m,y}$ is the
641 year and grid-cell specific monthly, m , mean temperature, H the Heaviside step function, 1mm
642 the threshold used to define wet days, and $P99.9_x$, the 99.9th percentile of historical (1979-

643 2019) daily precipitation at the grid-cell level. Units of the climate measures are degrees
644 Celsius for annual mean temperature and daily temperature variability, millimeters for total
645 annual precipitation and extreme daily precipitation, and simply the number of days for the
646 annual number of wet days.

647 We additionally calculated weighted standard deviations of monthly rainfall totals as also used
648 in ref. ⁸, but do not include them in our projections as we find that when accounting for delayed
649 effects their effect becomes statistically indistinct and is better captured by changes in total
650 annual rainfall.

651 **Spatial aggregation**

652 We aggregate grid-cell level historical and future climate measures, as well as grid-cell level
653 future GDPpc and population, to the level of the first administrative unit below national level
654 of the GADM database using an area-weighting algorithm which estimates the portion of each
655 grid-cell falling within an administrative boundary. We use this as our base-line specification
656 following previous findings that the effect of area or population weighting at the sub-national
657 level is negligible^{7,8}.

658 **Empirical model specification – fixed-effects distributed lag models**

659 Following a wide-range of climate econometric literature^{16,61}, we use panel regression models
660 with a selection of fixed-effects and time-trends to isolate plausibly exogenous variation with
661 which to maximise confidence in a causal interpretation of the effects of climate on economic
662 growth rates. The use of region fixed effects, μ_r , accounts for unobserved time-invariant
663 differences between regions such as prevailing climatic norms and growth rates due to
664 historical and geo-political factors. The use of yearly fixed effects, η_y , accounts for regionally
665 invariant annual shocks to the global climate or economy such as the El-Nino Southern
666 Oscillation or global recessions. [Following the literature](#), in our base-line specification we also
667 include region-specific [quadratic](#) time trends, $k_r y + \lambda_r y^2$, to exclude the possibility of

668 spurious correlations due to common slow-moving trends in climate and growth. The use of
 669 more conservative quadratic trends instead of just linear time trends was found to be less
 670 susceptible to potential outliers in the data and was based on the presence of long-term
 671 quadratic trends in the data (see Supplementary Figure 17) which therefore require these higher
 672 order controls⁶².

673 The persistence of climate impacts on economic growth rates is a key determinant of the long-
 674 term magnitude of damages. Methods for inferring the extent of persistence in impacts on
 675 growth rates have typically used lagged climate variables to evaluate the presence of delayed
 676 effects or catch up dynamics^{2,18}. For example, consider starting from a model in which a climate
 677 condition, $C_{r,y}$, (e.g. annual mean temperature) impacts the growth rate, $\Delta lgrp_{r,y}$ (the first
 678 difference of the logarithm of gross-regional product) of region r in year y :

$$679 \Delta lgrp_{r,y} = \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \alpha C_{r,y} + \varepsilon_{r,y}, \quad (4)$$

680 which we refer to as a “pure growth-effects” model in the main text. Typically, additional lags
 681 are included,

$$682 \Delta lgrp_{r,y} = \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \alpha_L C_{r,y-L} + \varepsilon_{r,y}, \quad (5)$$

683 and the cumulative effect of all lagged terms is evaluated to assess the extent to which climate
 684 impacts on growth rates persist. Following ref. ¹⁸, in the case that,

$$685 \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \alpha_L < 0 \text{ for } \alpha_0 < 0; \text{ or } \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \alpha_L > 0 \text{ for } \alpha_0 > 0 \quad (6)$$

686 the implication is that impacts on the growth rate persist up to NL years after the initial shock
 687 (possibly to a weaker or stronger extent), whereas if

$$688 \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \alpha_L = 0, \quad (7)$$

689 then the initial impact on the growth rate is recovered after NL years and the effect is only one
 690 on the level of output. However, we note that such approaches are limited by the fact that when
 691 including an insufficient number of lags to detect a recovery of the growth rates, one may find
 692 equation (6) to be satisfied and incorrectly assume that a change in climatic conditions impacts

693 the growth rate indefinitely. In practice, given a limited record of historical data, including too
 694 few lags to confidently conclude in an infinitely persistent impact on the growth rate is likely,
 695 particularly not over the long-timescales over which future climate damages are often
 696 projected^{2,24}. To avoid this issue, we instead begin our analysis with a model in which the level
 697 of output, $lgrp_{r,y}$, depends on the level of a climate variable, $C_{r,y}$:

$$698 \quad lgrp_{r,y} = \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \alpha C_{r,y} + \varepsilon_{r,y}. \quad (8)$$

699 Given the non-stationarity of the level of output, we follow the literature¹⁹ and estimate such
 700 an equation in first-differenced form as,

$$701 \quad \Delta lgrp_{r,y} = \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \alpha \Delta C_{r,y} + \varepsilon_{r,y}. \quad (8)$$

702 which we refer to as a model of “pure level-effects” in the main manuscript. This model
 703 constitutes a baseline specification in which a permanent change in the climate variable
 704 produces an instantaneous impact on the growth rate, and a permanent effect only on the level
 705 of output. By including lagged variables in this specification,

$$706 \quad \Delta lgrp_{r,y} = \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \alpha_L \Delta C_{r,y-L} + \varepsilon_{r,y}, \quad (9)$$

707 we are able to test whether the impacts on the growth rate persist any further than
 708 instantaneously by evaluating whether $\alpha_{L>0}$ are statistically significantly different from zero.

709 Even though this framework is also limited by the possibility of including too few lags, the
 710 choice of a baseline model specification in which impacts on the growth rate do not persist
 711 means that in the case of including too few lags, the framework reverts to the baseline
 712 specification of level-effects. As such, this framework is conservative with respect to the
 713 persistence of impacts and the magnitude of future damages. It naturally avoids assumptions
 714 of infinite persistence and we are able to interpret any persistence which we do identify with
 715 equation (9) as a lower-bound on the extent of climate impact persistence on growth rates. See
 716 the main text for further discussion of this specification choice, in particular regarding its
 717 conservative nature compared to previous literature estimates such as refs. ^{2,18}.

718 We allow the response to climatic changes to vary across regions, using interactions of the
719 climate variables with historical average (1979-2019) climatic conditions reflecting
720 heterogenous effects identified in previous work ^{7,8}. Following this previous work, the
721 moderating variables of these interaction terms constitute the historical average of either the
722 variable itself or of the seasonal temperature difference, \hat{T}_r , or annual mean temperature, \bar{T}_r , in
723 the case of daily temperature variability ⁷ and extreme daily rainfall, respectively ⁸.

724 The resulting regression equation with N and M lagged variables, respectively, reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
725 \Delta lgrp_{r,y} = & \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \sum_{L=0}^N (\alpha_{1,L} \Delta \bar{T}_{r,y-L} + \alpha_{2,L} \Delta \bar{T}_{r,y-L} \cdot \bar{T}_r) + \\
726 & \sum_{L=0}^N (\alpha_{3,L} \Delta \tilde{T}_{r,y-L} + \alpha_{4,L} \Delta \tilde{T}_{r,y-L} \cdot \hat{T}_r) + \sum_{L=0}^M (\alpha_{5,L} \Delta P_{r,y-L} + \alpha_{6,L} \Delta P_{r,y-L} \cdot P_r) + \\
727 & \sum_{L=0}^M (\alpha_{7,L} \Delta Pwd_{r,y-L} + \alpha_{8,L} \Delta Pwd_{r,y-L} \cdot Pwd_r) + \\
728 & \sum_{L=0}^M (\alpha_{9,L} \Delta Pext_{r,y-L} + \alpha_{10,L} \Delta Pext_{r,y-L} \cdot \bar{T}_r) + \epsilon_{r,y} \tag{10}
\end{aligned}$$

729 where $\Delta lgrp_{r,y}$ is the annual, regional GRPpc growth rate, measured as the first difference of
730 the logarithm of real GRPpc, following previous work^{2,3,7,8,18,19}. Fixed-effects regressions were
731 run using the `fixest` package in R⁶³.

732 Estimates of the coefficients of interest $\alpha_{i,L}$ are shown in Extended Data Figure 1 for $N=M=10$
733 lags and for our preferred choice of the number of lags in Supplementary Figures 2-4. We
734 assess uncertainty in these parameter estimates using the error specification of Conley⁶⁴, which
735 accounts for spatial autocorrelation between regions. Inter-regional distance is calculated based
736 on the distance between their centroids, and regions are assumed to have perfectly correlated
737 variables up to a cut-off distance of 500km using the uniform Kernel applied by the `fixest`
738 package⁶³. We use 500km as the primary cut-off distance because the correlations of residuals
739 in our models are very weak beyond 500km (Supplementary Figure 16) and Conley errors
740 assume full correlation up to to the cut-off distance, before which correlations of residuals
741 between regions are already well below 1. This also reflects the Rossby radius for mid-latitudes
742 which is the scale of weather systems and thus the physical constant that is underlying the

743 spatial correlation length in observational weather data⁶⁵. We also provide robustness tests
744 which assume autocorrelations up to 1000km or autocorrelation within countries (see
745 Supplementary Figure 15). We primarily address spatial correlation using Conley errors
746 because this is agnostic to the size of countries which varies substantially within our sample.

747 **Spatial-lag model**

748 In Supplementary Figure 14 we present the results from a spatial-lag model which explores the
749 potential for climate impacts to “spill-over” into spatially neighboring regions. We measure
750 the distance between centroids of each pair of sub-national regions and construct spatial-lags
751 which take the average of the first-differenced climate variables and their interaction terms
752 over neighboring regions which are at distances of 0-500, 500-1000, 1000-1500 and 1500-
753 200km (spatial lags, “SL”, 1 to 4). For simplicity, we then assess a spatial lag model without
754 temporal lags to assess spatial spillovers of contemporaneous climate impacts. This model
755 takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
756 \quad \Delta lgrp_{r,y} = & \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \sum_{SL=0}^N (\alpha_{1,SL} \Delta \bar{T}_{r-SL,y} + \alpha_{2,SL} \Delta \bar{T}_{r-SL,y} \cdot \bar{T}_{r-SL}) + \\
757 \quad & \sum_{SL=0}^N (\alpha_{3,SL} \Delta \tilde{T}_{r-SL,y} + \alpha_{4,SL} \Delta \tilde{T}_{r-SL,y} \cdot \hat{T}_{r-SL}) + \sum_{SL=0}^N (\alpha_{5,SL} \Delta P_{r-SL,y} + \alpha_{6,SL} \Delta P_{r-SL,y} \cdot \\
758 \quad & P_{r-SL}) + \sum_{SL=0}^N (\alpha_{7,SL} \Delta Pwd_{r-SL,y} + \alpha_{8,SL} \Delta Pwd_{r-SL,y} \cdot Pwd_{r-SL}) + \\
759 \quad & \sum_{SL=0}^N (\alpha_{9,SL} \Delta Pext_{r-SL,y} + \alpha_{10,SL} \Delta Pext_{r-SL,y} \cdot \bar{T}_{r-SL}) + \epsilon_{r,y} \quad (11)
\end{aligned}$$

760 where SL indicates the spatial lag of each climate variable and interaction term. In
761 Supplementary Figure 14 we plot the cumulative marginal effect of each climate variable at
762 different baseline climate conditions by summing the coefficients for each climate variable and
763 interaction term, for example for average temperature impacts as:

$$764 \quad ME = \sum_{SL=0}^N (\alpha_{1,SL} + \alpha_{2,SL} \bar{T}_{r-SL}) \quad (12)$$

765 These cumulative marginal effects can be regarded as the overall spatially dependent impact
766 to an individual region given a 1-unit shock to a climate variable in that region and all
767 neighboring regions at a given value of the moderating variable of the interaction term.

768 **Constructing projections of economic damage from future climate change**

769 We construct projections of future climate damages by applying the coefficients estimated in
770 equation (10) and shown in Supplementary Tables 2-4 (when including only lags with notable
771 effects in specifications which limit overfitting, see Supplementary Methods Section S1) to
772 projections of future climate change from the CMIP-6 models. Year-on-year changes in each
773 primary climate variable of interest are calculated to reflect the year-to-year variations used in
774 the empirical models. 30-year moving averages of the moderating variables of the interaction
775 terms are calculated to reflect the long-term average of climatic conditions which were used
776 for the moderating variables in the empirical models. By using moving averages in the
777 projections, we account for the changing vulnerability to climate shocks based on the evolving
778 long-term conditions (Supplementary Figures 10 & 11 show that the results are robust to the
779 precise choice of the window of this moving average). While these climate variables are not
780 differenced, the fact that the bias-adjusted climate models reproduce observed climatological
781 patterns across regions for these moderating variables very accurately (Supplementary Table
782 6) with limited spread across models (<3%) precludes the possibility that any considerable bias
783 or uncertainty is introduced by this methodological choice. However, we impose caps on these
784 moderating variables at the 95th percentile at which they were observed in the historical data,
785 in order to prevent extrapolation of the marginal effects outside of the range in which the
786 regressions were estimated. This is a conservative choice which limits the magnitude of our
787 damage projections.

788 Time-series of primary climate variables and moderating climate variables are then combined
789 with estimates of the empirical model parameters to evaluate equation (10), producing a time
790 series of annual GRPpc growth rate reductions for a given emission scenario, climate model
791 and set of empirical model parameters. The resulting time series of growth rate impacts reflect
792 those occurring due to future climate change. By contrast, a future scenario with no-climate

793 change would be one in which climate variables do not change (other than with random year-
794 to-year fluctuations), and hence the time-averaged evaluation of equation (10) would be zero.
795 Our approach therefore implicitly compares the future climate change scenario to this no-
796 climate change baseline scenario.

797 The time-series of growth rate impacts due to future climate change in region r and year y , $\delta_{r,y}$,
798 are then added to the future baseline growth rates, $\pi_{r,y}$, (in log-diff form) obtained from the
799 SSP2 scenario to yield trajectories of damaged GRPpc growth rates, $\rho_{r,y}$. These trajectories
800 are aggregated across time to estimate the future trajectory of GRPpc with future climate
801 impacts:

$$802 \quad GRPpc_{r,Y} = GRPpc_{r,2020} \sum_{y=2020}^Y \rho_{r,y} = GRPpc_{r,2020} \sum_{y=2020}^Y (1 + \pi_{r,y} + \delta_{r,y})$$

803 (13)

804 where $GRPpc_{r,y=2020}$ is the initial log-level of GRPpc. We begin damage estimates in 2020 to
805 reflect the damages occurring since the end of the period for which we estimate the empirical
806 models (1979-2019) and to match the timing of mitigation cost estimates from most IAMs (see
807 below).

808 For each emission scenario, this procedure is repeated 1000 times while randomly sampling
809 from the selection of climate models, the selection of empirical models with different numbers
810 of lags (shown in Supplementary Figures 1-3 and Supplementary Tables 2-4), and [the](#)
811 [covariance matrix for the parameter estimates from each empirical model](#). The result is an
812 ensemble of future GRPpc trajectories which reflect uncertainty from both physical climate
813 change and the structural and sampling uncertainty of the empirical models.

814 **Estimates of mitigation costs**

815 We obtain IPCC estimates of the aggregate costs of emission mitigation from the AR6 Scenario
816 Explorer and Database hosted by IIASA²³. Specifically, we search the AR6 Scenarios Database
817 World v1.1 for Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) which provided estimates of global GDP

818 and population under both an SSP2 baseline and SSP2-RCP2.6 scenario in order to maintain
819 consistency with the socio-economic and emission scenarios of the climate damage projections.
820 We find five IAMs which provide data for these scenarios, namely MESSAGE-GLOBIOM
821 1.0, REMIND-MAgPIE 1.5, AIM/GCE 2.0, GCAM 4.2, and WITCH-GLOBIOM 3.1. Of these
822 five, we use results only from the first three which passed the IPCC vetting procedure for
823 reproducing historical emission and climate trajectories. We then estimate global mitigation
824 costs as the percentage difference in global per capita GDP between the SSP2 baseline and the
825 SSP2-RCP2.6 emission scenario. In the case of one of these IAMs, estimates of mitigation
826 costs begin in 2020 while in the case of two others mitigation costs begin in 2010. The
827 mitigation cost estimates prior to 2020 in these two IAMs are mostly negligible, and our choice
828 to begin comparison to damage estimates in 2020 is conservative with respect to the relative
829 weight of climate damages compared to mitigation costs for these two IAMs.
830

831 **Data availability**

832 Data on economic production and ERA-5 climate data are both publicly available at

833 <https://zenodo.org/records/13773040>, and

834 <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5> respectively. Data on

835 mitigation costs are publicly available at <https://data.ene.iiasa.ac.at/ar6/#/downloads>.

836 Processed climate and economic data, as well as all other necessary data for reproduction of

837 the results are available at the public repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/13957801>.

838 **Code availability**

839 All code necessary for reproduction of the results is available at the public repository:

840 <https://zenodo.org/records/13957801>.

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- 905

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913 underlying economic data.

914 **Author contributions**

915 All authors contributed to the design of the analysis. MK conducted the analysis and
916 produced the Figures. All authors contributed to the interpretation and presentation of the
917 results. MK and LW wrote the manuscript.

918 **Competing interest declaration**

919 We have no competing interests to declare.

920 **Additional information**

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926 **Extended Data Figure 1. Constraining the persistence of historical climate impacts on**

927 **economic growth rates.** The results of a panel fixed effects distributed lag model for the

928 effects of annual mean temperature (a), daily temperature variability (b), total annual

929 precipitation (c), the number of wet days (d) and extreme daily precipitation (e) on sub-

930 national economic growth rates. Point estimates show the effects of a one degree Celsius or

931 one standard deviation increase (for temperature and precipitation variables respectively) at

932 the lower quartile, median and upper quartile of the relevant moderating variable (green,

933 orange, purple, respectively) at different lagged periods after the initial shock (note that these

934 are not cumulative effects). Climate variables are used in their first-differenced form (see

935 main text for discussion), and the moderating climate variables are the annual mean

936 temperature, seasonal temperature difference, total annual precipitation, number of wet days,

937 and annual mean temperature respectively in panels (a-e) (see methods for further

938 discussion). Error bars show the 95% confidence intervals [with errors assuming that variables](#)

939 [are fully correlated up to distances of 500km between centroids of sub-national regions,](#)

940 [following Conley⁶⁴, and implemented within the FEOLS package in R⁶³.](#) The within-region

941 R-squared, Bayesian and Akaike Information criteria for the model are shown at the top of
942 the figure. This figure shows results with ten lags for each variable to demonstrate the
943 observed levels of persistence, but our preferred specifications remove later lags based on the
944 [distribution](#) of the terms shown above and the Information Criteria shown in Extended Data
945 Figure 2. The resulting models without later lags are shown in Supplementary Figures 1-3.
946

947

948 **Extended Data Figure 2. Incremental lag selection procedure using information criteria**

949 **and within-region R².** Starting from a panel fixed effects distributed lag model estimating

950 the effects of climate on economic growth using the real historical data (as in equation 4 of

951 the main manuscript) with ten lags for all climate variables (as shown in Extended Data

952 Figure 1), lags are incrementally removed for one climate variable at a time. The resulting

953 Bayesian and Akaike Information Criteria are shown in columns (a-e) and (f-j) respectively,

954 and the within-region R-squared and number of observations in columns (k-o) and (p-t).
955 Different rows show the results when removing lags from different climate variables, ordered
956 from top to bottom as annual mean temperature, daily temperature variability, total annual
957 precipitation, the number of wet days, and extreme annual precipitation. Information Criteria
958 show minima at approximately four lags for precipitation variables and ten to eight for
959 temperature variables, indicating that including these numbers of lags does not lead to
960 overfitting. See Supplementary Table 1 for an assessment using Information Criteria to
961 determine whether including additional climate variables causes overfitting.
962

963

964 **Extended Data Figure 3. Damages in our preferred specification which provides a**
 965 **robust lower-bound on the persistence of climate impacts on economic growth vs**
 966 **damages in specifications of pure growth or pure level effects.** Estimates of future
 967 damages as shown in Figure 1 of the main manuscript, but under the emission scenario
 968 RCP8.5 for three separate empirical specifications: in orange our preferred specification
 969 which provides an empirical lower-bound on the persistence of climate impacts on economic
 970 growth rates while avoiding assumptions of infinite persistence (see main text for further
 971 discussion); in purple a specification of “pure growth effects” in which the first difference of
 972 climate variables is not taken and no lagged climate variables are included (the baseline
 973 specification of ref²); and in pink a specification of “pure level effects” in which the first

974 difference of climate variables is taken but no lagged terms are included. Shading represents
975 the 34% confidence intervals reflecting the *likely* range (following the likelihood
976 classification adopted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change), having accounted
977 for different sources of uncertainty as outlined in Figure 1.
978

979

980

Extended Data Figure 4. Climate changes in different variables as a function of

981

historical interannual variability. Changes in each climate variable of interest from 1979-

982

2019 to 2035-2065 under the high-emission scenario SSP5-RCP8.5, expressed as a

983

percentage of the historical variability of each measure. Historical variability is estimated as

984

the standard deviation of each detrended climate variable over the period 1979-2019 over

985

which the empirical models were identified (detrending is appropriate due to the inclusion of

986

region-specific linear time trends in the empirical models). See Figure S15 for changes

987

expressed in standard units. Data on national administrative boundaries are obtained from the

988

GADM database version 3.6 and are freely available for academic use (<https://gadm.org/>).

989

990

991

992 **Extended Data Figure 5. Contribution of different climate variables to overall**

993 **committed damages.** (a) Climate damages in 2050 when using empirical models which
 994 account for all climate variables, changes in annual mean temperature only, or changes in
 995 both annual mean temperature and one other climate variables (daily temperature variability,
 996 total annual precipitation, the number of wet days and extreme daily precipitation

997 respectively). **Uncertainty ranges indicate the likely (66%) range across uncertainty as**

998 **described in the caption to Fig. 1.** (b) The cumulative marginal effects of an increase in

999 annual mean temperature of one degree, at different baseline temperatures, estimated from

1000 empirical models including all climate variables or annual mean temperature only. Estimates

1001 and uncertainty bars represent the median and 95% confidence intervals obtained from 1000

1002 samples from each of three different empirical models using eight, nine or ten lags of

1003 temperature terms, **and the uncertainty of the covariance structure of their parameter**

1004 **estimates using Conley errors⁶⁴ with a spatial cut-off distance of 500km.**

1005

1006

1007 **Extended Data Figure 6. The difference in committed damages between the upper and**

1008 **lower quartiles of countries when ranked by GDP and cumulative historical emissions.**

1009 Quartiles are defined using a population weighting, as are the average committed damages

1010 across each quartile group. The violin plots indicate the distribution of differences between

1011 quartiles across the two extreme emission scenarios (RCP2.6 and RCP8.5) and the

1012 uncertainty sampling procedure outlined in the methods section which accounts for

1013 uncertainty arising from the choice of lags in the empirical models, uncertainty in the

1014 empirical model parameter estimates, as well as the climate model projections. Bars indicate

1015 the median, as well as the 10 and 90th percentiles and upper and lower sixths of the

1016 distribution reflecting the very likely and likely ranges following the likelihood classification

1017 adopted by the IPCC.

1018

Climate Variable	Physical mechanisms	References
Average annual temperature	Labour productivity and supply; agricultural productivity	Dasgupta et al. (2021) ⁶⁶ ; Lobell et al. (2013) ⁶⁷ , Zhao et al. (2017) ⁶⁸
Daily temperature variability	Agricultural productivity; physical health; mental health	Wheeler et al. (2000) ⁶⁹ , Rowhani et al. (2011) ⁷⁰ , Ceglar et al. (2016) ⁷¹ ; Shi et al. (2015) ⁷² ; Xue et al. (2019) ⁷³
Total annual precipitation	Agricultural productivity; metropolitan labour outcomes; conflict	Liang et al. (2017) ⁷⁴ ; Desbreaux et al. (2019) ⁷⁵ ; Damania et al. (2020) ⁷⁶
Number of wet days	Travel disruption	Lacking
Extreme daily precipitation	Flood damages; disruption	Davenport et al. (2021) ⁷⁷ , Dave et al. (2021) ⁷⁸

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Extended Data Table 1. A summary of several physical mechanisms that plausibly

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underlie the impact of the different climate variables on macroeconomic growth, with

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references to empirical evidence. This summary is not intended to be an exhaustive list of

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all mechanisms or references. In the case of most climate variables a number of plausible

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physical mechanisms supported by empirical evidence exist. The only exception here is the

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number of wet days for which plausible mechanisms are listed but empirical evidence does

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not yet exist (as far as the authors are aware). The use of the number of wet days in the main

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empirical models is therefore guided primarily by the empirical evidence indicating robust

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impacts on economic growth⁸.

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Variable	Formula	Lag 0	Lag 1	Lag 2	Lag 3	Lag 4	Lag 5	Lag 6	Lag 7	Lag 8	Lag 9	Lag 10
Annual mean temperature	$\Delta\tilde{T}_{r,y}$	0.12 (0.7)	-0.33 (0.99)	-0.48 (1)	0.41 (1.1)	0.78 (1.3)	0.75 (1.4)	1.9 (1.5)	1.3 (1.3)	-0.6 (1.2)	-0.14 (0.9)	-1.7* (0.74)
	$\Delta\tilde{T}_{r,y}.\tilde{T}_r$	-0.12* (0.062)	-0.16* (0.078)	-0.1 (0.081)	-0.17 (0.09)	-0.21* (0.099)	-0.27* (0.11)	-0.31** (0.11)	-0.26** (0.092)	-0.15* (0.073)	-0.013 (0.074)	-0.013 (0.043)
Daily temp. variability	$\Delta\tilde{T}_{r,y}$	-7.3* (3.2)	-3.3 (5.1)	-9 (5.7)	-5.8 (5.9)	0.95 (7.2)	-2.8 (6.5)	-3.9 (5.8)	-5.8 (5.3)	-1.1 (4.4)	-9.7** (3.7)	-3.3 (2.5)
	$\Delta\tilde{T}_{r,y}.\tilde{T}_r$	0.045 (0.12)	-0.21 (0.19)	0.015 (0.19)	-0.058 (0.22)	-0.3 (0.26)	-0.13 (0.24)	-0.082 (0.21)	-0.022 (0.19)	-0.047 (0.17)	0.3* (0.13)	0.11 (0.098)
Total annual precip.	$\Delta P_{r,y}$	0.0026 (0.0031)	0.0071 (0.0043)	0.0047 (0.0052)	0.0038 (0.0053)	0.0021 (0.0052)	0.0015 (0.0044)	0.0019 (0.0043)	-0.00099 (0.0042)	-0.0017 (0.0036)	0.00013 (0.0031)	7e-06 (0.0023)
	$\Delta P_{r,y}.\tilde{P}_r$	-2.6e-07 (1.2e-06)	-2e-06 (1.7e-06)	-5.6e-07 (1.9e-06)	-1.2e-06 (1.9e-06)	-1.3e-06 (1.9e-06)	-4.5e-07 (1.8e-06)	-7.6e-07 (1.7e-06)	2e-07 (1.7e-06)	1.8e-07 (1.6e-06)	-9e-07 (1.4e-06)	-5.5e-07 (9.2e-07)
Annual no. wet days	$\Delta Pwd_{r,y}$	-0.091 (0.058)	-0.091 (0.081)	0.00041 (0.11)	-0.037 (0.1)	0.021 (0.12)	0.012 (0.13)	-0.065 (0.13)	0.037 (0.12)	0.083 (0.1)	0.059 (0.1)	0.012 (0.048)
	$\Delta Pwd_{r,y}.\tilde{P}wd_r$	0.00058 (0.00035)	0.00047 (0.00047)	-0.00029 (0.0006)	0.00016 (0.00058)	-5.7e-05 (0.00065)	-0.00027 (0.00076)	0.00021 (0.00073)	-0.0003 (0.00077)	-0.00065 (0.00067)	-0.00057 (0.00065)	-2.4e-05 (0.00029)
Daily precip. extremes	$\Delta Pext_{r,y}$	-0.022* (0.01)	-0.023 (0.014)	-0.012 (0.015)	-0.011 (0.016)	0.0044 (0.018)	0.0042 (0.017)	-0.0014 (0.019)	0.0008 (0.015)	0.0033 (0.015)	0.0069 (0.013)	0.011 (0.0097)
	$\Delta Pext_{r,y}.\tilde{T}_r$	0.00061 (0.00041)	0.00059 (0.0006)	3.8e-05 (0.00067)	7e-05 (0.00076)	-0.00035 (0.00083)	-0.00012 (0.00084)	0.00011 (0.0009)	-5.6e-05 (0.00081)	-0.00034 (0.00077)	-0.00024 (0.00072)	-0.0005 (0.00047)
R2	0.407											
WR2	0.0602											
BIC	-227											
AIC	-4.33e+04											
N	34855											

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1031 **Extended Data Table 2. Regression results for the historical effects of different climate**
1032 **variables on sub-national economic growth rates in the period 1979-2019.** Numbers show
1033 the point estimates for the effect of each climate variable and their interaction term on sub-
1034 national economic growth rates (in percentage points), having estimated eq. (4) with ten lags
1035 for each climate variable (i.e. each table entry denotes a specific regression coefficient $\alpha_{X,L}$ of
1036 the same model as indicated in equation 4). Standard errors are shown below in parenthesis
1037 and *, ** and *** denote significance at the 5, 1 and 0.1% levels [using the error specification](#)
1038 [of Conley with a cut-off distance of 500km to address spatial auto-correlation](#). Formulas for
1039 climate variables and their interaction terms are denoted as in equation (4) of the main
1040 methods. Note that an interpretation of the significance of the effects of a given climate
1041 variable requires an assessment of both the coefficient of the climate variable itself as well as
1042 its interaction term. Extended Data Figure 1 provides the opportunity for such an
1043 interpretation by plotting the estimated marginal effects with confidence intervals. The R-
1044 squared, within-region R-squared (the R-squared along the temporal dimension), Akaike
1045 Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and number of

1046 observations are also shown. Cut-off distances of 500km may be too large for precipitation

1047 variables which typically show weaker spatial autocorrelation¹⁶.

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Study	Resolution	Number of climate variables	Baseline specification of growth- or level-effects	Number of lags	Damages by 2100 under RCP8.5
Burke et al. (2015) ²	National	One	Growth	None	25%
Kahn et al. (2019) ³⁵	National	One	Level	Four	7.2%
Kalkuhl & Wenz (2020) ³	Sub-national	One	Level	One	14.2%
This study	Sub-national	Five	Level	Eight-ten/four	59.9%

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1050 **Extended Data Table 3. A comparison of the magnitude of estimated economic damage**

1051 **from future climate change across recent panel-based empirical studies.** All studies use

1052 fixed effects panel regressions. The first four columns describe differences in the underlying

1053 data and empirical specification. The third column shows the nature of the baseline

1054 specification without lags with regards to growth or level effects (see main text for further

1055 discussion). The last column compares projections of future economic damage under RCP-

1056 8.5 by 2100 as reported by the respective study.

Supplementary Information for:

Update to: The economic commitment of climate change

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Supplementary overview

This document provides supplementary information for the manuscript “[Update to: The economic commitment of climate change](#)”. Within can be found:

1. Supplementary methods on robustness tests of the empirical models:
 1. Section S1: Limiting overfitting
 2. Section S2: Robustness to autocorrelation in the climate variables
 3. Section S3: Robustness to cross-correlation in the climate variables
 4. Section S4: Restricted distributed lag model.
2. Supplementary Discussion
 1. Section S5: The magnitude of damages in the context of historical economic development
3. Supplementary Figures 1-18.
4. Supplementary Tables 1-6.

References herein are listed separately to those appearing in the main manuscript.

Supplementary Methods:

Robustness tests of the empirical models

Section S1: Limiting overfitting

Our empirical models contain five climate variables, each included with a number of lags. These choices are made to reflect previous literature which identified multiple climatic conditions with significant impacts on economic output¹⁻³, as well as to identify the extent of persistence with which these climatic conditions impact growth (see main text and methods). The use of a large number of independent variables may raise concerns that the empirical models may overfit the data and as such provide inaccurate estimations of the impacts from future climate change. We assess this possibility by using the Bayesian and Aikake Information Criteria (BIC and AIC) to compare empirical models with and without different climate variables and when including different numbers of lags. BIC and AIC are evaluated using a trade-off between the maximized likelihood function and penalties for additional model terms which could result in overfitting. As such, they can be used to assess the relative strength of different models in terms of best describing the data and limiting the possibility of overfitting.

Section S1.1: Limiting overfitting with regards to multiple climate variables

Supplementary Table 1 compares our main model including all climate variables to models which sequentially exclude individual climate variables. In general, the BIC and AIC indicate a preference for the original model with all climate variables compared to models which lack other variables. This indicates that the model with all climate variables provides the best trade-off between best describing the data and including additional terms which could cause overfitting. The only exception here is that when removing the measure of extreme daily rainfall, the BIC indicates a preference for the model without extreme daily rainfall, whereas

the AIC indicates a preference for the model with extreme daily rainfall. BIC is a more conservative measure⁴ which provides superior performance in selecting the true model from a set of alternatives⁵. Given the epistemological inexistence of a “true model” of the reality of climate impacts, the fact that AIC is often superior in selecting models which will generalise better to new data⁵ (i.e. projecting impacts under climate change), and the fact that the parameters of the extreme daily rainfall metric are statistically significant (Extended Data Figure 1, Extended Data Table 2, Supplementary Figures 1-3, and Supplementary Tables 2-4), we continue to include extreme daily rainfall in our empirical model.

Section 1.2: Limiting overfitting due to the inclusion of lagged variables

Extended Data Figure 2 compares models with different numbers of lags to assess the extent to which including lags may cause overfitting. The analysis begins with a model with ten lags for each climate variable, and sequentially excludes lags from one climate variable at a time. The BIC and AIC show minima at approximately four lags for precipitation variables, supporting the choice of four lags which was made when considering the [distribution](#) of lagged terms (Extended Data Figure 1, Extended Data Table 2). For the temperature terms, minima in AIC and BIC are found at approximately eight to ten lags, further supporting the choice of lags made based on [the distribution of lag parameters](#) (Extended Data Figure 1, Extended Data Table 2).

These analyses indicate that including all climate variables with four lags for precipitation and eight to ten for temperature terms provides the best trade-off between describing the data and including more terms which could cause overfitting. Moreover, the Monte-Carlo simulations outlined in Section S2 demonstrate that Information Criteria can act as an effective indicator for selecting an appropriate number of lags (see Section S2 and Supplementary Figure 6).

Section S1.3 Alternative methods to limit overfitting

AIC and BIC metrics support our choice of climate variables and number of lags, indicating that they provide a preferable trade-off between maximizing variance and limiting overfitting. Alternative methods exist which could fulfil similar functions in selecting models which optimize this trade-off. In particular, cross-validation provides an asymptotically equivalent approach⁶, which may be particularly attractive in the context of prediction problems. Cross-validation splits the available data into two parts, first training the empirical model with one set before testing it on the other. This yields a direct evaluation of the ability of the empirical model to predict new data.

The aim of this paper, however, is not to accurately predict economic growth, but to project the exogenous impact of future climate conditions on the economy, based on robustly inferred causal relationships, and assuming *ceteris paribus* (compare previous climate-economy literature, e.g. refs. (1,7,8)). That is, factors important for predicting economic growth such as technological development, wars, pandemics and financial crises are assumed constant. As a consequence, the main objective of the model selection procedure is to provide a robust identification strategy for causal inference⁹⁻¹¹. In particular, our empirical model is based on a careful selection of fixed-effects and regional time-trends to isolate variation in climate and economic growth which are plausibly exogenous, and a careful choice of climate variables in their first-differenced form with a number of lags to provide a lower-bound on the persistence of impacts on growth (see main text section “A robust lower bound on the persistence of climate impacts on growth” and methods section “Empirical models – fixed-effects distributed lag models”). Given this emphasis on inference rather than prediction in the identification of plausibly causal empirical models and the projection of exogenous impacts; the asymptotic equivalence of Information Criteria and cross-validation for model

selection⁶; and the fact that AIC and BIC indicate that our empirical models already provide a preferable trade-off between maximizing variance and limiting overfitting, we do not pursue cross-validation as a further method for model selection. Cross-validation nevertheless offers an interesting avenue for further work on the prediction of economic growth in the context of climate impacts which is beyond the scope of this manuscript.

Section S2: Robustness to autocorrelation in the climate variables

When using lagged climate variables, the presence of autocorrelation (Supplementary Figure 4) may raise concerns regarding imperfect multicollinearity in the empirical models. Developing upon the methodology used by ref. ¹², we conduct Monte-Carlo simulations in which real climate data is randomly reassigned to different regions and a known effect is artificially added to the economic data to test whether this produces biased or imprecise parameter estimates (Supplementary Figure 5a-d).

Specifically, we choose an effect, α , of 2%-points per degree C increase in temperature to mimic the magnitude of effect sizes which we detect in the real data (Extended Data Figure 1). Moreover, we allow this effect to persist for a number of years after the initial shock which we refer to as the persistence time, p . The original time series of economic growth, $g_{r,y}$, is updated based on the newly assigned temperature time series, $\bar{T}_{r,y}$, according to the equation,

$$\tilde{g}_{r,y} = g_{r,y} + \alpha(\bar{T}_{r,y} - \bar{T}_{r,y-p}). \quad (S1)$$

This procedure is repeated 100 times to produce an ensemble of artificial datasets with known effects of temperature changes on economic growth which preserve the structure of the temperature time-series, including its autocorrelation. We then run panel fixed effects distributed lag models of the same structure as outlined in equation (10) in the Methods

section (but in this case including only a single climate variable as independent variable without interaction terms), to test the efficacy of the models in obtaining the true parameter estimates in the presence of autocorrelation.

The results are shown in Supplementary Figure 5 for models with different numbers of lags applied to artificial data in which effects of different persistence times have been added. Results indicate that despite the presence of autocorrelation in the temperature time series (Supplementary Figure 4), the empirical models obtain accurate and precise estimates of the true regression parameters. We further quantify the systematic and random errors in these model estimates explicitly by measuring the percentage difference between the cumulative true parameters (as added to the data) and estimated parameters (as obtained from the empirical models), as well as the standard deviation of parameter estimates across Monte-Carlo simulations. These estimates are shown in Supplementary Figure 6 alongside Information Criteria from the empirical models estimated on the artificial datasets. Results demonstrate that despite the presence of autocorrelation, random error is very small, although it increases with the number of lags, in particular when this number greatly exceeds the persistence times (Supplementary Figure 5i-l & 6a-c). By contrast, including an insufficient number of lags to adequately capture the extent of impact persistence can systematically underestimate the cumulative impact of a climatic change (Supplementary Figure 5i-l & Figure 6a-c), a direct result of the conservative nature of our empirical specification using the first difference of climate variables as outlined in the main text.

As well as demonstrating the robustness of the empirical models in the presence of autocorrelation, these results also indicate that Information Criteria typically used for model selection may provide a useful diagnostic for an incremental model selection when reducing the number of lags from a larger initial number (Supplementary Figure 6d-f). This further

supports the use of Information Criteria for selecting an appropriate number of lags, as used in Extended Data Figure 2 and outlined in Section S1. While these tests focus on the role of annual mean temperature only, the results generalize to other variables as made clear in the second set of Monte-Carlo simulations described in Section S3 and shown in Supplementary Figure 7.

Section S3: Robustness to cross-correlation in the climate variables

A second set of Monte-Carlo simulations aims to test the robustness of the empirical models to cross correlations between different climate variables (Supplementary Figure 4f). The simulation procedure follows the same as that outlined above, but effects from all five climate variables are added into the data simultaneously following equivalent procedures as in equation (S1). Importantly, time series of the different climate variables are re-assigned together to preserve their cross-correlative structure. Effect sizes and persistence times are chosen to reflect those observed in the real data for each variable, corresponding to $\alpha = 2, 5, 0.008, 0.2$ and 0.02 per unit increase of each climate variable for annual mean temperature, daily temperature variability, total annual precipitation, annual number of wet days and extreme daily rainfall respectively (these appear different to the magnitudes shown in Extended Data Figure 1 for precipitation variables because effect sizes in this figure have been scaled by the within-region standard deviation of each precipitation variable), and to $p=8, 8, 4, 4,$ and 4 for the respective variables. Panel fixed effects distributed lag models are then applied to the artificial datasets as outlined in equation (10) in the Methods section, in one case including only individual climate variables as independent variables, and in the other case including all climate variables simultaneously. The results shown in Figure 7 indicate that cross correlations between climate variables only produce biased estimates when climate

variables are assessed individually; simultaneously including all variables in the models is necessary to adequately capture the effect of individual variables.

Section S4: Restricted distributed lag model

Minor oscillations in the point estimates for the effects of annual mean temperature may indicate the influence of autocorrelation (Extended Data Figure 1). While the results of our Monte-Carlo simulations suggest that such influence is negligible (Supplementary Figures 5 and 6), we nevertheless investigate whether the use of a restricted distributed lag model limits these effects^{13,14}.

Restricted distributed lag models are often used to limit the potential oscillations and imprecision caused by autocorrelation in the independent variables, by constraining the lagged parameters to follow a particular function¹⁵. Motivated by the distribution of unrestricted lags observed with ten lags for all climate variables (Extended Data Figure 1), which generally grow and then decay at varying rates, we choose a quadratic function to approximate the distribution.

Given a single variable distributed lag model with lag coefficients, β_L , and the assumption of a quadratic distribution of these coefficients,

$$\beta_L = \vartheta_0 + \vartheta_1 L + \vartheta_2 L^2, \quad (\text{S2})$$

the distributed lag model may be simplified according to the following transformation:

$$g_{r,y} = \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \beta_L \bar{T}_{r,y-L} + \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \varepsilon_{r,y} \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$g_{r,y} = \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \vartheta_0 \bar{T}_{r,y-L} + \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \vartheta_1 L \bar{T}_{r,y-L} + \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \vartheta_2 L^2 \bar{T}_{r,y-L} + \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \varepsilon_{r,y} \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$g_{r,y} = \vartheta_0 Z0_{r,y} + \vartheta_1 Z1_{r,y} + \vartheta_2 Z2_{r,y} + \mu_r + \eta_y + k_r y + \lambda_r y^2 + \varepsilon_{r,y}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where

$$Z0_{r,y} = \sum_{L=0}^{NL} \bar{T}_{r,y-L}, Z1_{r,y} = \sum_{L=0}^{NL} L \cdot \bar{T}_{r,y-L}, Z2_{r,y} = \sum_{L=0}^{NL} L^2 \bar{T}_{r,y-L}. \quad (S6)$$

This simplifying transformation reduces the number of parameters required to estimate the distribution of lagged effects, limiting imprecision and smoothing oscillatory behavior which are potentially introduced by autocorrelation in the independent variable. We apply the above transformation to all independent variables in equation (10) of the main manuscript (i.e., all climate variables and their interaction terms), estimate panel fixed-effects regressions on these transformed variables, and then display the estimated distribution of lagged effects in Supplementary Figure 8.

Using a quadratic lag distribution reduces oscillations (Supplementary Fig 8) but provides cumulative effects of a similar magnitude to the un-restricted model for annual mean temperature (Supplementary Fig 9a). This likely reflects the fact that, even when severe, imperfect multicollinearity causes correlated parameter biases¹³ which consequently do not introduce errors in out of sample predictions¹⁶. In this context, this implies that if oscillatory biases in the lagged parameters were present due to autocorrelation (which Supplementary Methods Section S2 suggests is not the case), then these biases would anyway be correlated in such a way as not to introduce bias to the cumulative lagged effects (because if one lag is biased larger, another will be biased smaller). This suggests that our initial un-restricted lag model is suitable for projecting future damages which depend primarily on the cumulative lagged effects. We therefore continue to use the un-restricted model as our main specification, also due to its more flexible form which appears to provide a better description of the lag distribution for the temperature variability and extreme rainfall variables in particular (compare Extended Data Figure 1 to Supplementary Figure 8, and further see Supplementary Figure 9).

Supplementary Discussion

Section S5: The magnitude of damages in the context of historical economic development

We here provide a discussion of the plausibility of the magnitude of projected climate damages, in light of the historical damages which they imply, and the background of historical economic development. In particular, this discussion addresses whether magnitudes and patterns of historical economic development make the magnitude and heterogeneity of damages which we project implausible. These discussions can be considered as “back-of-the-envelope” calculations, to estimate and compare approximate magnitudes.

The world has experienced approximately 1C of global warming historically since 1970¹⁷, and CMIP6 climate models project approximately another 1C of global warming by 2050 (compared to 2020) under SSP585 (see IPCC AR6 WG1¹⁸, Figure4.2). This makes for a convenient and approximate comparison of the future damages which we project against those which we should have experienced historically since 1970, allowing a contextualisation against the background of historical economic development. We calculate an approximate 20% reduction in global GDP from the additional 1C of global warming projected under SSP585 (Figure1), with differences between the upper and lower quartile of the income distribution of approximately 13.6%-points (Extended Data Figure 6), meaning a maximal impact of around 30% reduction in developing countries compared to 10% reduction in more wealthy countries. Let us assume that the historical 1C of global warming produced damages of similar magnitudes, although in reality they were likely smaller due to the non-linear response to average temperature which is more negative as regions warm (Extended Data Figure 1). We can then compare the magnitude of these damages to the background economic development which occurred between 1970 and 2020. Average growth rates of GDP per capita were approximately 1.8% over the past 50 years¹⁹, implying an average growth

in GDP per capita of over 140% since 1970. Taking the bottom quartile of countries by World Bank income per capita (using 2015 values) gives average growth rates of 0.84% annually over the past 50 years, whereas the upper quartile of countries gives average growth rates of 1.41% annually (note that this is consistent with evidence that absolute income convergence has not occurred historically, see refs. ²⁰⁻²²). These imply overall income per capita growth of 52% and 101% in the lower- and upper-income quartiles respectively over the past 50 years (noting that the greatest income growth has occurred for countries in the middle quartiles).

Even given the approximate nature of these calculations, it becomes quite clear that while considerable, the implied damages of historical climate change (20%) are unlikely to have had consequences which are inconsistent with historical economic development (an increase in income per capita of 140%) or obviously noticeable without an appropriate no-climate-change counterfactual to which to compare. Moreover, poorer regions have actually seen lower growth rates than richer regions historically. Our estimates indicate that climate change may have played a role in this, and that the gap between them would have been smaller (approx. $52+30=82\%$ vs $101+10=111\%$) without climate change. However, the observation of lower growth rates in poor versus rich countries can in no way be interpreted as causal evidence of historical climate damages because of the large unobserved biases which influence differences across countries which are unrelated to climate. There is no counterfactual world without climate change from which we can measure whether poorer and richer countries are *actually* 30% and 10% worse off than they would have been without climate change. Therefore, we must rely on the empirical approaches such as the one taken here based on fixed-effects panel regressions to identify impacts which are plausibly causal.

Nevertheless, these “back-of-the-envelope” calculations demonstrate that the magnitude of damages which we project is consistent with historical developments, given that: a) historical economic development is much larger than the historical damages implied by our analysis, b) richer regions grew historically at faster rates than poorer regions, consistent with the pattern of climate damages we show, and in which historical climate change therefore potentially played a contributing role.

Supplementary Figure 1. Results of a panel fixed effects distributed lag model with eight lags for temperature terms and four for precipitation terms. As Extended Data Figure 1 but using eight lags for the temperature terms and four lags for the precipitation terms.

Supplementary Figure 2. Results of a panel fixed effects distributed lag model with nine lags for temperature terms and four for precipitation terms. As Extended Data Figure 1 but using nine lags for the temperature terms and four lags for the precipitation terms.

Supplementary Figure 3. Results of a panel fixed effects distributed lag model with ten lags for temperature terms and four for precipitation terms. As Extended Data Figure 1 but using ten lags for the temperature terms and four lags for the precipitation terms.

Supplementary Figure 4. Assessing auto- and cross-correlations in the climate variables identified as drivers of climate impacts on economic output. (a-e) Correlation matrices between lagged variables to assess auto-correlation in annual mean temperature, $\Delta\bar{T}$, daily temperature variability, $\Delta\tilde{T}$, total annual precipitation, ΔP , the annual number of wet days, ΔP_{wd} , and the measure of extreme daily precipitation, ΔP_{ext} , (see methods for further details of these definitions). (f) Correlation matrices between the different climate variables. All values show the average Pearson correlation obtained from each of the 1660 regions on which the effects of climatic changes on economic output are estimated. Note that in all cases, climate variables are assessed in their first differenced form to reflect the way in which they are used in the empirical models.

Supplementary Figure 5. Results of Monte-Carlo simulations to assess the robustness of

the empirical models to autocorrelations in the climate time series, as well as to demonstrate the conservative nature of our approach which underestimates the magnitude of impacts when an insufficient number of lags are included. Grey circles indicate the true parameters describing the effect of a change in climate on economic growth rates as added into the data during the Monte-Carlo simulation procedure which randomly reassigned real temperature time series to different regions (see SI Methods Section S1). Red crosses indicate the average and vertical lines the standard deviation of estimates of these parameters from panel fixed-effects distributed lag models based on 100 Monte-Carlo simulations. Panels (a-d) show the results for an effect which persists for three years, when including an increasing number of lags (two, four, six, ten) in the regressions, while panels (e-h) and (i-l) show the equivalent results for an effect which persists for five and eight years respectively. The average within-region R-squared values (variance explained along the temporal dimension) across models of the different simulations are indicated above each panel.

Supplementary Figure 6. Random and systematic errors in model parameter estimates, as well as Information Criteria at different levels of climate impact persistence and different numbers of lags as obtained from the results of Monte-Carlo simulations. Results of the same Monte-Carlo simulations presented in Supplementary Figure S5, in which effects of different persistence times (three, five and eight) are added into the economic data after a random reassignment of temperature time series and are then detected using different numbers of lags (one to ten) in panel fixed effects distributed lag models (see SI methods section S1). Panels (a-c) display the standard deviation of parameter estimates across Monte-Carlo simulations averaged across the lagged parameters, expressed as a percentage of the true parameter magnitude (in red); also shown is the percentage difference between the cumulative lagged parameter estimates and the true cumulative lagged parameters (blue). The first measure reflects random error, whereas the second measure reflects systematic error in the parameter estimates. In the case of the second measure, solid lines show the average and confidence intervals the 5th and 95th percentiles across the 100 Monte-Carlo simulations. Results indicate that an insufficient number of lags with respect to the true level of impact persistence causes an underestimation of the true effect, while the inclusion of a larger number of lags can increase random error. Panels (d-f) display the Akaike and Bayesian Information Criteria (AIC/BIC) which are typically used to select between alternative models by penalizing overfitting (note that lower values indicate a better model). Results show that a lag selection process based on information criteria and

incremental model changes only provides useful indications for the appropriate number of lags when starting from a large initial number and then decreasing.

Supplementary Figure 7. Results of Monte-Carlo simulations to assess the robustness of the empirical models to imperfect multicollinearity arising from cross-correlations between different climate variables. Grey circles indicate the true parameters describing the effect of a change in climate on economic growth rates as added into the data during the Monte-Carlo simulation procedure which randomly reassigned real time series of all climate variables to different regions (see methods). The effect sizes and persistence of the

effects of the different climate variables are chosen to mimic those identified in the real historical data (Extended Data Figure 1). Red crosses indicate the average and vertical lines the standard deviation of estimates of these parameters from fixed-effects panel regressions based on 100 Monte-Carlo simulations. Panels (a-e) show results from empirical models in which only a single climate variable was included as an independent variable, whereas panels (f-j) show results from models in which all climate variables were included simultaneously. The within-region R-squared values (variance explained along the temporal dimension; wr^2), and Akaike and Bayesian Information Criteria on average across models of the different simulations (AIC, BIC) are given above each panel. Results of the simulations indicate that, given the real co-linearities between climate variables, including all climate variables simultaneously in the regressions is necessary to accurately capture the separate effects of the individual variables (compare left and right columns).

Supplementary Figure 8. Results of a panel fixed effects restricted distributed lag model for the effects of climatic changes on economic output using a quadratic lag distribution.

See Supplementary Methods Section S3 for details of the transformation of lagged variables used to produce a quadratic distribution. Ten lags are used for temperature terms but only four for precipitation terms to enable an appropriate fitting of a quadratic function to the distribution of lagged effects observed in the un-restricted model shown in Extended Data

Figure 1. Figure is otherwise structured as Extended Data Figure 1.

Supplementary Figure 9. Comparison of the cumulative marginal effects of climate variables on economic output when using a restricted and unrestricted distributed lag model. The cumulative marginal effects of annual mean temperature (a), daily temperature variability (b), total annual precipitation (c), the annual number of wet days (d) and extreme daily precipitation (e) are shown at different values of the moderating variable (x-axis) having been estimated from the restricted and un-restricted distributed lag models with ten lags for temperature and four lags for precipitation terms respectively, as shown in Supplementary Figures 3 & 8. Cumulative marginal effects are in most cases statistically indistinguishable between the models, with particularly close estimates for annual mean temperature (a) for which the restricted lag model was motivated (see main text). Larger differences between the cumulative marginal effects of the two models in the other climate variables likely arise when a quadratic function does not provide a good fit to the un-restricted distribution of lags, in particular for daily temperature variability (b) and extreme daily precipitation (e) which exhibit different lag distributions at different values of the

moderating variables (see Extended Data Figure 1). This suggests that for these variables the more flexible un-restricted distributed lag model provides a better description of the delayed effects.

Supplementary Figure 10. Robustness test of the timescale with which changes in the moderating variable of the empirical models are estimated. As Figure 1 of the main manuscript but when evaluating changes in the moderating variables of the interaction terms in the empirical models based on 10-year averages rather than 30-year averages. See methods for further details.

Supplementary Figure 11. Robustness test of the timescale with which changes in the moderating variable of the empirical models are estimated. As Figure 1 of the main manuscript but when evaluating changes in the moderating variables of the interaction terms in the empirical models based on 20-year averages rather than 30-year averages. See methods for further details.

Supplementary Figure 12. Robustness test of the choice of method used for accounting for sub-national price changes. As Figure 1 but having used results obtained from fixed-effects panel models applied to estimates of sub-national real output per capita based on the application of national-level GDP deflators prior to the use of currency conversions (see methods for further details).

Supplementary Figure 13. Climate changes in different variables. Changes in each climate variable of interest from 1979-2019 to 2035-2065 under the high-emission scenario SSP5-RCP8.5. Data on national administrative boundaries are obtained from the GADM database version 3.6 and are freely available for academic use (<https://gadm.org/>).

wr2=0.0146/BIC=-1912/AIC=-4.387e+04

Supplementary Figure 14. Exploration of possible spill-over effects of contemporaneous climate impacts on spatially neighbouring regions. Panels (a-e) show the cumulative impacts of different climate variables on economic growth rates when including the spatially lagged-effects of climate shocks in neighbouring regions with centroids a distance of up to 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000km away (1, 2, 3 or 4 spatial lags, respectively). Spatial lags are constructed by taking the average of the first-differenced climate variables and their interaction terms over neighboring regions (see methods for detail). Due to data availability constraints, these models do not account for spill-overs which may occur via trade, and for simplicity they use no temporal lags of the climate variables, therefore only reflecting contemporaneous impacts. Error bars show the 95% confidence intervals using Conley errors with a cut-off distance of 500km. See the Methods section of the main manuscript for further details.

Supplementary Figure 15. Robustness of the results to the removal of Uzbekistan. Panel a: estimates of the cumulative marginal impact of one degree of warming in annual mean temperature when dropping individual countries from the sample are shown in grey, with the special case of Uzbekistan highlighted in red. Panel b: The distribution of committed global damages for the full data set and having removed data from Uzbekistan either completely or prior to 2000, respectively. The median is indicated by the white bar, the interquartile range by the inner box.

Supplementary Figure 16. Robustness of estimates to spatial autocorrelation. Panel a: the correlations of model residuals between pairs of regions as a function of interregional distance are shown as the individual black dots. The mean value of pairwise correlations within bins of 50km width is shown in red. The preferred cut-off distance of 500km is shown by the vertical dashed blue line. Conley standard errors assume full correlation between regions up to that cut-off distance. Panel b: the distribution of committed global damages is shown for different standard error specifications, using Conley standard errors with cut-offs of 500km and 1000km, and clustering by region or country-year.

Supplementary Figure 17. Damage estimates using national level World Bank data. Here we show a robustness test which uses national level data on GDP per capita from the World Bank¹⁹ and equivalent econometric approaches to estimating damages: i.e. using the first difference of climate variables (in this case only annual mean temperature) with a number of lags. Panel (a) shows the marginal effect of a given temperature increase, with significant effects detected up to around 20 lags, based on uncertainty assessments using Driscoll-Kraay²³ standard errors which account for all forms of spatial and temporal autocorrelation as well as heteroskedasticity. Panel (b) shows the projected global damages based on this econometric specification, which provide further support for the qualitative conclusions of the manuscript: namely that damages before mid-century are consistent across emission scenarios and larger than mitigation costs but diverge substantially thereafter.

Supplementary Figure 18. Underlying trends in economic growth. Examples of underlying trends in economic growth for the largest region (by population) in a selection of major countries across continents. Data are plotted with the seaborn python package, showing the result of fitting a quadratic trend to the data with 90% confidence intervals (command “regplot”). The examples demonstrate the presence of region-specific non-linear long-term trends in underlying economic growth. Moreover, the examples show that when trends are not highly non-linear, the coefficient for the quadratic term will be close to zero such that essentially only a linear trend will be fitted (as in the cases of California and São Paulo).

<i>Climate measure removed</i>	None (full model)	Daily temp. variability	Total annual rainfall	Annual number of wet days	Extreme daily precip.
AIC	-43686.55	-43033.32	-43591.70	-43596.17	-43634.81
BIC	-856.8742	-355.7585	-846.5287	-851.0039	-889.6377

Supplementary Table 1. Information criteria to assess model overfitting when removing additional climate variables. Akaike and Bayesian Information criteria to assess the relative strength of models which include either all climate variables or remove individual variables. The models here use eight lags for temperature and four for precipitation terms as indicated in Supplementary Figure 1 to be optimal for limiting overfitting in terms of lag selection. Lower information criteria indicate a better model in terms of explaining a greater amount of variance while limiting overfitting by penalising additional terms. Both criteria indicate that including all climate variables provides the best model in terms of limiting overfitting, except the more conservative BIC^{4,5} measure when considering extreme daily precipitation.

Variable	Lag 0	Lag 1	Lag 2	Lag 3	Lag 4	Lag 5	Lag 6	Lag 7	Lag 8
Annual mean temperature	0.23 (0.67)	-0.5 (0.99)	-0.58 (1)	0.71 (1.1)	0.97 (1.1)	0.94 (1.1)	2.4* (1.1)	1.5 (0.78)	-0.45 (0.64)
	-0.09 (0.066)	-0.092 (0.08)	-0.042 (0.084)	-0.12 (0.091)	-0.16 (0.09)	-0.21* (0.086)	-0.25** (0.077)	-0.21** (0.067)	-0.1* (0.05)
Daily temp. variability	-5.4 (3.2)	1.1 (5.1)	-2.7 (5.6)	2 (5.8)	9.6 (6.6)	6.6 (5.7)	5.8 (4.5)	3.6 (3.5)	9.3** (3)
	-0.0055 (0.12)	-0.34 (0.19)	-0.17 (0.19)	-0.29 (0.21)	-0.55* (0.24)	-0.4 (0.21)	-0.38* (0.17)	-0.3* (0.13)	-0.37** (0.11)
Total annual precip.	0.0027 (0.0029)	0.0078* (0.0038)	0.0054 (0.0039)	0.0045 (0.0032)	0.0023 (0.0028)				
	-1.3e-07 (1.2e-06)	-2.1e-06 (1.5e-06)	-8e-07 (1.5e-06)	-1.4e-06 (1.2e-06)	-1.4e-06 (1e-06)				
Annual no. wet days	-0.098 (0.061)	-0.12 (0.078)	-0.037 (0.085)	-0.076 (0.075)	-0.016 (0.059)				
	0.0006 (0.00037)	0.00068 (0.00048)	3.4e-05 (0.00051)	0.0005 (0.00045)	0.0003 (0.00033)				
Daily precip. extremes	-0.023** (0.0089)	-0.025* (0.011)	-0.017 (0.012)	-0.016 (0.013)	-0.00077 (0.0092)				
	0.00066 (0.00036)	0.00063 (0.00048)	0.00024 (0.00049)	0.00021 (0.00053)	-0.00015 (0.0004)				
R2	0.385								
WR2	0.0413								
BIC	-857								
AIC	-4.37e+04								
N	34855								

Supplementary Table 2. Regression results for the historical effects of different climate variables on sub-national economic growth rates in the period 1979-2019. As Extended Data Table 2 but including eight time lags for the temperature terms four time lags for the precipitation terms.

Variable	Lag 0	Lag 1	Lag 2	Lag 3	Lag 4	Lag 5	Lag 6	Lag 7	Lag 8	Lag 9
Annual mean temperature	0.43	0.17	0.39	1.7	2.2	2.5	3.7**	2.8*	0.99	1.5*
	(0.66)	(0.99)	(1)	(1.1)	(1.2)	(1.3)	(1.4)	(1.1)	(0.95)	(0.63)
	-0.12	-0.13	-0.081	-0.14	-0.18	-0.22*	-0.25*	-0.2*	-0.1	0.025
	(0.061)	(0.078)	(0.082)	(0.092)	(0.099)	(0.1)	(0.1)	(0.087)	(0.063)	(0.066)
Daily temp. variability	-6.7*	-1.6	-6.7	-3.2	3	-0.48	-0.43	-2.4	2.8	-5.7*
	(3.1)	(5)	(5.6)	(5.8)	(6.9)	(6.2)	(5.1)	(4.6)	(3.9)	(2.6)
	0.037	-0.25	-0.042	-0.12	-0.33	-0.17	-0.16	-0.097	-0.15	0.19
	(0.11)	(0.18)	(0.19)	(0.21)	(0.24)	(0.22)	(0.18)	(0.17)	(0.15)	(0.098)
Total annual precip.	0.0019	0.0067	0.0043	0.0034	0.0012					
	(0.0028)	(0.0036)	(0.0038)	(0.003)	(0.0027)					
	7.9e-08	-1.8e-06	-4.7e-07	-1.1e-06	-1.1e-06					
	(1.1e-06)	(1.4e-06)	(1.4e-06)	(1.2e-06)	(1e-06)					
Annual no. wet days	-0.08	-0.088	-0.015	-0.051	0.00074					
	(0.055)	(0.072)	(0.089)	(0.071)	(0.057)					
	0.00052	0.00052	-6.2e-05	0.00038	0.00025					
	(0.00033)	(0.00043)	(0.00052)	(0.00042)	(0.00033)					
Daily precip. extremes	-0.024**	-0.025*	-0.017	-0.016	-0.00082					
	(0.0089)	(0.012)	(0.013)	(0.013)	(0.009)					
	0.00068	0.00067	0.00019	0.00022	-0.00016					
	(0.00036)	(0.0005)	(0.0005)	(0.00052)	(0.00039)					
R2	0.396									
WR2	0.0502									
BIC	-648									
AIC	-4.34e+04									
N	34855									

Supplementary Table 3. Regression results for the historical effects of different climate variables on sub-national economic growth rates in the period 1979-2019. As Extended Data Table 2 but including nine time lags for the temperature terms and four time lags for the precipitation terms.

Variable	Lag 0	Lag 1	Lag 2	Lag 3	Lag 4	Lag 5	Lag 6	Lag 7	Lag 8	Lag 9	Lag 10
Annual mean temperature	0.18 (0.7) -0.12* (0.062)	-0.27 (1) -0.15* (0.077)	-0.4 (1) -0.1 (0.082)	0.56 (1.2) -0.18 (0.09)	0.9 (1.3) -0.21* (0.099)	0.92 (1.4) -0.27* (0.11)	2.1 (1.6) -0.31** (0.11)	1.4 (1.4) -0.26** (0.095)	-0.53 (1.2) -0.14 (0.074)	0.0094 (0.92) -0.0052 (0.079)	-1.6* (0.73) -0.017 (0.044)
Daily temp. variability	-7.1* (3.1) 0.043 (0.12)	-3.3 (5) -0.21 (0.18)	-8.8 (5.6) 0.0089 (0.19)	-5.8 (5.9) -0.053 (0.22)	0.9 (7.3) -0.29 (0.26)	-2.7 (6.6) -0.13 (0.24)	-3.4 (5.9) -0.091 (0.21)	-5.5 (5.4) -0.027 (0.19)	-0.8 (4.5) -0.056 (0.17)	-8.9* (3.8) 0.29* (0.14)	-3.3 (2.5) 0.11 (0.099)
Total annual precip	0.0021 (0.0029) 2e-08 (1.1e-06)	0.0065 (0.0036) -1.7e-06 (1.4e-06)	0.004 (0.0038) -2.6e-07 (1.4e-06)	0.0026 (0.0031) -8.4e-07 (1.2e-06)	0.00087 (0.0028) -9.5e-07 (1.1e-06)						
Annual no. wet days	-0.088 (0.058) 0.00058 (0.00035)	-0.096 (0.074) 0.00056 (0.00045)	-0.008 (0.086) -0.00014 (0.00051)	-0.04 (0.07) 0.0003 (0.00042)	0.012 (0.057) 0.00017 (0.00034)						
Daily precip. extremes	-0.023* (0.0093) 0.00066 (0.00037)	-0.025* (0.012) 0.00065 (0.00049)	-0.015 (0.012) 0.00012 (0.00047)	-0.014 (0.013) 0.00013 (0.00051)	0.00049 (0.0095) -0.00023 (0.00039)						
R2	0.403										
WR2	0.0549										
BIC	-415										
AIC	-4.31e+04										
N	34855										

Supplementary Table 4. Regression results for the historical effects of different climate variables on sub-national economic growth rates in the period 1979-2019. As Extended Data Table 2 but including ten time lags for the temperature terms and four time lags for the precipitation terms.

GFDL-ESM4	CNRM-CM6-1	BCC-CSM2-MR	KACE-1-0-G
IPSL-CM6A-LR	CNRM-ESM2-1	CAMS-CSM1-0	NESM3
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	EC-Earth3	CESM2	TaiESM1
MRI-ESM2-0	MIROC6	FGOALS-g3	
UKESM1-0-LL	ACCESS-ESM1-5	IITM-ESM	
CanESM5	AWI-CM-1-1-MR	INM-CM5-0	

Supplementary Table 5. List of climate models from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase-6 used to project future climate change.

<i>Climate measure</i>	Annual mean temperature	Seasonal temperature difference	Total annual rainfall	Annual number of wet days
<i>Pearson correlation to observations</i>	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.998
<i>Average absolute percentage error to observations</i>	0.2%	2.1%	1.2%	2.8%
<i>Coefficient of variation across climate models</i>	0.0038	0.018	0.018	0.030

Supplementary Table 6. Evaluation of systematic bias and uncertainty in bias-adjusted climate model output over the historical period 1979-2015. The first row shows Pearson correlations between regional climate data from the mean of the bias-adjusted CMIP-6^{24,25} ensemble and the W5E5 observational dataset²⁶ for the different climate variables used as moderating variables of the interaction terms of the empirical models and in the projections of future damages. The second row shows the absolute percentage difference between the climate data from the two sources, averaged across regions. The third row shows the coefficient of variation (standard deviation divided by the mean) of each climate measure across climate models, averaged across regions.

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